

D8.4 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION FINAL REPORT

Mona Marill, Natalia Cediél, AUS

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ABSTRACT

This report presents the ASHVIN project's achievements in communication and dissemination of activities and results. This is a central part of the project, enabling to sustain the research results among the targeted stakeholders, beyond the project's ending. Moreover, this report focuses on presenting the related activities and results from the last project term, from M19 onwards but it also offers an overview of the aggregated results enabling to assess the overall impact.

KEYWORDS

Digital Twin, Building Information Modelling, Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation, Standardisation, Impact, Planning, Strategy

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AEC	Architectural Engineering and Construction
BIM	Building Information Modelling
C&D	Communication & Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DT	Digital Twin
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SDO	International Standardisation Organisation
WP	Work Package

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open-source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behavior of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main objective of communication and dissemination activities of the ASHVIN project has been to position ASHVIN as a European benchmark in the application of Digital Twin (DT) technologies to the construction sector, stating its potential to foster productivity, efficiency, safety, and sustainability of the sector, with clear-cut benefits beyond Building Information Modelling (BIM).

Communication and dissemination are a crucial part of the success for all Horizon2020 projects funded by the European Commission, as this enables to promote the project and its results but also to build public awareness about the ASHVIN's contributions to the digital transformation of the building sector with the digital twin technology. Therefore, from the very start of the project, the entire consortium contributed proactively to this task. The objectives for communication and dissemination were set in the Grant Agreement, and **now we confirm having successfully met all the fixed objectives and have gone beyond these original intentions** (see Section 3).

The **ASHVIN stakeholders** that were at the core of the dissemination and communication activities are either direct or indirect beneficiaries of the developed technological solution. ASHVIN activities were addressed to over **90 organisations** and **6750+ individuals**. We have reached out continuously to the different stakeholder groups, spreading the results of the research work, to demonstrate the usability and usefulness of the ASHVIN solution and leveraging the project's results in technological innovation. Now, our aim is to make the ASHVIN project's work sustainable, and make sure that these stakeholders make the use the ASHVIN innovation and research outcomes beyond the project's duration.

In the communication activities, the ASHVIN project has adopted a mixed marketing portfolio approach which focus on showcasing the project's progress in research and development novel digital twin solution. In social media, with presence and a tailored editorial calendar in LinkedIn and X, the project has gained in total **3100+ followers**. The project website has engaged **a monthly average of 310 users**, with over **100 published knowledge blog articles** about the project. In addition, the stakeholders have been invited to take part in the **interactive technical webinars** counting in **total 130 participants**. **Moreover**, we published **10 newsletters** to share outcomes, opportunities, and news from ASHVIN and its sister projects.

In dissemination, the ASHVIN project has made the research and technological development results openly available with continuous efforts throughout the project. At the time of this deliverable submission, our team has published in total **19 peer-reviewed scientific publications, including 12 publications in scientific conferences** and **7 publications in scientific journals, all in open access**. As a project, ASHVIN has been presented at **59 related events** (in total) worldwide, where the partners gave keynote presentations, seminars, lectures and **5 workshops**. Moreover, we have drafted **37 public deliverables** in the project.

All openly available scientific publications and public deliverables have been shared in open access via **Zenodo, counting over 3200+ downloads in total.**

Thanks to this continuous engagement, we have built **an active community around the project.** Firstly, **the cluster of four projects, ASHVIN, BIMProve, COGITO and BIM2Twin,** that were funded under the same Horizon2020 call (LC-EEB-008) have leveraged their outreach and dissemination activities by organising joint workshops and co-authoring publications. Secondly, **18 external stakeholders from the ASHVIN demonstration sites, at 10+ European locations,** have been involved in the demo testing of the ASHVIN tools, which has enabled to interact with the target end-users of the system and consider their feedback as considering the commercial exploitation and fine-tuning of the ASHVIN system. And thirdly, **the advisory board of 6 experts in the digital transformation of AEC industry** has followed the entire ASHVIN project's journey and provided us with insights from the sector and feedback to continue the research while meeting the market's expectations.

The legacy of the project's research communication and dissemination will be sustained by the partners and their dedicated researchers, developers, and managers. For instance, we have learnt in our communication campaign, #ResearchStories, in which we presented ASHVIN's researchers, that most of our researchers will continue working on the topics they were devoted to in the project. Further, the ASHVIN marketing team will sustain the ASHVIN website two-years after the project's ending date making the results available in open access. Also, all publications will remain openly accessible, without any limit date. This way, we ensure the most meaningful research results of the project will continue supporting the digital transformation of the construction sector, even beyond the project's ending.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Dissemination and communication go hand in hand in all research and innovation projects supported by the European Union, with the objective to raise awareness of the project and to share the results with the target stakeholders. In our ASHVIN project, **D8.1 ASHVIN Impact Master Plan**¹ set the strategy for this task, and **D8.2 Dissemination & Communication Interim Report**² provided a status update at the project month 18 (March 2022).

The European Commission underlines the importance of the communication for all EU-funded projects³: *“A comprehensive communication strategy is crucial to promote your project and its results. Your plan should define clear objectives adapted to a range of target audiences. It should be proportionate to the scale of your project”*. The Commission also specifies that dissemination is about sharing research results with the scientific community, commercial players, civil society, and policymakers. In both cases, it is a matter of **creating the impact of the research’s results among the target stakeholders**, and this has been one of the guiding principles in the ASHVIN dissemination and communication activities throughout the project.

This report presents the results of the ASHVIN stakeholder engagement, communication, and dissemination activities from the 2nd project-half, from April 2022 (M19) until the end of the project, March 2024 (M42).

The overall assessment of the results and the Key Performance Indicators status include the results from the entire project period showcasing that all set objectives have been met.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/4392312>

² <https://zenodo.org/records/6405239>

³ European Commission, European Research Executive Agency, *Are you communicating your Horizon Europe project?*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2848/078892>

2 STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION FRAMEWORK

A cornerstone of ASHVIN’s communication and dissemination framework are the target stakeholders to whom all the performed activities were directed towards. These groups benefit either directly or indirectly of the research and digital technology results delivered by the project. In this context, communication is seen as a tool for informing stakeholders about ASHVIN’s innovation whereas dissemination is a tool for ensuring the uptake and deployment of results by the stakeholders. In total, over **90 organisations** (further detailed in the next sections) and **6800+ individuals** (counting participants in events where the ASHVIN project was presented, participants in the ASHVIN webinars, and followers in social media) followed and benefitted directly from the ASHVIN’s research during the project.

2.1 Community Building Cycles

All partners continue an agile management of the ASHVIN stakeholders’ community, including scouting new and contacting all stakeholders. The agile community building cycles were based on key project moments; as soon as we had a key milestone to share with the community (webinar, scientific publication, or major technical deliverable) in the project, we promoted it directly towards the identified stakeholders. The promotion was done in the established communication channels but also by one-to-one contacts managed by all ASHVIN partners.

Table 1 ASHVIN's Community Building Cycles M18 - M42

Milestone	Timing
Continuous scientific publications	Every month
M18 Deliverables	March 2022 -
M24 Deliverables	September 2022 -
M30 Deliverables	October 2023 -
ASHVIN Open Call for demonstrators	February 2023 -
Webinar #1	February 2023
Webinar #2	May 2023
Webinar #3	February 2024
M42 Deliverables	March 2024
Project’s legacy & assets	February – March 2024

During the last project-half (M18-M42), the most important community building aspect of the project was to find and recruit new demonstrators using the developed digital twin platform and tools (as a part of WP7 Demonstrators). Thanks to the good existing connections of the consortium members and relentless engagement, 15 new demonstrators’ sites were added to the project (read more about the KPI50 Demo Site communication in

5.9.1). Also, another crucial part of the stakeholder engagement was the partners' participation in all kinds of events enabling to share the results of their research and to build synergies with other related initiatives.

2.2 ASHVIN Stakeholder Mapping at M42

ASHVIN's target stakeholders are organised in six different categories with the most important actors being **construction industry**, **digital twin technology providers** and **digital transformation advocates** who are at the nexus of transforming the construction sector with digital twins (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 ASHVIN Stakeholder Groups

We targeted our stakeholders with the mixed communication portfolio combining online and offline communication activities (website, flyers, continuous social media presence, audiovisual material, webinars etc.), completed with a range of dissemination activities (events, scientific publications, and open data).

All individuals, organisations and companies that have benefitted directly from the ASHVIN's research activities and results. The following sections provide insights from the different addressed external stakeholders. All these groups were directly engaged via one-to-one contacts, communication channels or event participation during the different community building cycles (see Table 1).

2.3 Construction industry

The construction industry stakeholders cover predominantly construction site and infrastructure asset owners, construction site managers and workers, asset maintenance managers as well as material suppliers. This group is at the core of the project as the objective is to develop and validate a digital twin solution enhancing the project management of construction and infrastructure assets in the three different phases, including design, construction, and maintenance.

The ten ASHVIN demonstration sites have **directly involved 18 external stakeholders** and two ASHVIN partners (NCC and FASADA) from the construction sector. They have enabled running the ASHVIN field experiments at their premises (buildings, bridges, motorways, airport runways, roof structures) enabling partners to collect data that help to create the ASHVIN digital twin toolkit as well as digital twin representation of the demonstration sites. Therefore, their involvement has been crucial to the success of the project, and it has been widely communicated with the demonstration site campaign (see Figure 2). In addition, the 16 additional demo sites recruited during the last project year with the ASHVIN open call involved **new additional stakeholders** contributing to these experiments (as reported in Deliverable 7.4). Figure 2 showcases the key stakeholders from the construction sector involved in the ASHVIN Demonstration Sites.

Figure 2 ASHVIN Demo Site Stakeholders

In addition, the following table lists these stakeholders, specifying the related demo site.

Table 2 List of the ASHVIN Demo Sites' External Stakeholders

Name	Website	Related ASHVIN Demo Site
DRACE GEOCISA	https://www.drace.com/	Demo Site #1
Renfe	https://www.renfe.com/	
Adif	https://www.adif.es/inicio	
Municipal Buildings and Housing Administration of Gdynia (ZBiLK)	https://zbilk.gdynia.pl/	Demo Site #2
Zadar Airport	https://www.zadar-airport.hr/en	Demo Site #3
Dragados	https://www.dragados.com/	Demo Site #6
BCA	http://bcarq.com/estudio/	

BIS	http://www.bisstructures.com/en/	
FREO	https://www.freogroup.com/	
The Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda, Spain (MITMA)	https://www.mitma.gob.es/	Demo Site #7
BAGH Técnica	https://www.bagh.es/	
City of Dortmund - Civil engineering department	www.dortmund.de	Demo Site #8
Terrabiota	www.terrabiota.de	
Stadtwerke München (SWM)	https://www.swm.de/	Demo Site #9
City of Munich	https://www.muenchen.de/	
Olympiapark München GmbH (OMG)	https://www.olympiapark.de/	
Port of Rotterdam	https://www.portofrotterdam.com/en	Demo Site #10

2.4 Digital twin tech providers

This group gathers technology industry and start-ups, universities and RTOs developing digital twin technologies, privacy, and security providers as well as SDOs and ESOs. Over **30 stakeholder organisations from this group have directly benefited from ASHVIN's dissemination activities** (webinars, scientific or non-scientific event presentations and publications). Along with the construction industry, these actors are at the core of the ASHVIN project and the exploitation beyond the project lifetime.

The project directly reached **26 universities across the world**, and the ASHVIN partners joined their hosted conferences, presented the project for their members, gave workshops, lectures, and seminars.

Figure 3 ASHVIN's Academic Stakeholders

In line with Figure 3, the following table lists the researched academic stakeholders and precises have the ASHVIN project interacted with them.

Table 3 Stakeholder universities and scientific organisations

Organisation Name & Country	Link	ASHVIN's Contribution
University of Amsterdam, Netherlands	www.uva.nl/en	Event – Publication in Conference proceedings (MMM2024)
National Academy of Engineering, The United States	www.nae.edu	Event – Publication in Conference proceedings (TRB 2024)
the University of Sydney, the Digital Sciences Initiative, Australia	https://dsi.sydney.edu.au/	Event – Workshop (2023)
The University of Melbourne, the Centre for Spatial Data Infrastructures & Land Administration, Australia	https://eng.unimelb.edu.au/csdlia	Event – Seminar (2023)
ETH Zürich, Switzerland	https://ethz.ch	Event –Publication of conference proceedings (Eurosteel 2023)
Bouwen met Staal, Netherlands	www.bouwenmetstaal.nl	
Delft University of Technology, Netherlands	www.tudelft.nl	
the International Group of Lean	www.iglc.net	Event –Publication of conference

Construction		proceedings (IGLC 2023)
“Gheorghe Asachi” Technical University of Iasi, Romania	https://www.tuiasi.ro/?lang=en	Event – Lecture to students and presentation at CCE 2023.
University of Bergen, Norway	https://www.uib.no/en	Event – and Scientific conference proceeding publication at MMM 2023
Chung -Ang University, Korea	https://neweng.cau.ac.kr/index.do	Event – Workshop hosting (CONVR 2022)
The Technical University of Madrid, the School of Industrial Engineers Spain	https://www.industriales.upm.es/	Event – Keynote presentation (at Jornada de Digitalización de Infraestructuras Lineales)
Cornell Tech, the United States	https://tech.cornell.edu/	Event – Keynote presentation (at Contextual Integrity Symposium 2022)
Structural Stability Research Council, Canada	https://www.ssrcweb.org/	Event – and Scientific conference proceeding publication at ICSS 2022
Aarhus University, Department of Civil and Architectural Engineering, Denmark	https://international.au.dk/	Event – Keynote presentation (at the EG-ICE 29 th)
Huazhong University of Science and Technology, China	https://english.hust.edu.cn/	Followed an ASHVIN webinar series given by TUB for HUST.
Colorado School of Mines, The United States	www.mines.edu	Represented at the ASHVIN Advisory Board (Dr. H. Sebnem Düzgün)
Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong	www.polyu.edu.hk	Represented at the ASHVIN Advisory Board (Prof. Heng Li)
Stanford University, The United States	www.stanford.edu	Represented at the ASHVIN Advisory Board (Prof. Martin Fischer)
University of Waterloo, Canada	https://uwaterloo.ca/	Represented at the ASHVIN Advisory Board (Prof. Carl Haas)
Beijing Jiatong University., Institute of Ancient Structures, China	http://en.njtu.edu.cn/	Invited Lecture January 2024
University of Notre Dame, the United States	https://www.nd.edu/	Invited Lecture April 2023
University of Texas in Austin, the United States	https://www.utexas.edu/	Invited Lecture October 2023.
Texas A&M University, the United States	https://www.tamu.edu/	Invited Lecture October 2023 (Rolando Chacón and Timo Hartmann). Two independent events
Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden	https://www.chalmers.se/en/	Invited Lecture November 2023.

Also, the project exchanged with **four other major actors** that promote digital twin technologies for the construction sector, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 ASHVIN's Industry Stakeholders

Related to this, the following table lists these actors and how the project engagement with them.

Table 4 ASHVIN's Stakeholders Promoting Digital Twin Industry

Name	Link	ASHVIN's Contribution
Ferrovial Austin	https://www.ferrovial.com/	Event. Meeting October 2023
OAC Services, Inc	https://oacsvcs.com/	Represented in the ASHVIN advisory board.
Think IoT Group	https://www.rfid-wiot-search.com/about-rfid-and-wireless-iot/	Event – Online lecture (Think WIoT Day 2023)
CEN/CENELEC TC 442 /WG9 Digital Twins in Built Environments	Access	Contribution in the ongoing standardisation work, participation in the WG meetings. This effort was managed under the WP6 by ASI.

2.5 Digital transformation advocates

The digital transformation advocates group include EU construction associations, green building councils and digital innovation hubs. These all promote the benefits of digitalisation of the construction industry organising events, meetings, and workshops. In total, the project members collaborated with over **8 different advocate organisations**, as shown in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable..**

Figure 5 Stakeholders - Advocate Organisations

The following table lists these stakeholders sharing how the project contributed to the organisation’s activities.

Table 5 List of Advocate Organisations

Name	Website	ASHVIN’s Contribution
ECTP platform	https://www.ectp.org/	- Two events (February 2024 and March 2022)
Building Smart International	www.buildingsmart.org/	- Using the Building Smart Use Case models to represent ASHVIN use cases. - Events – Building Smart Poland & Romania.
International Council for Research and Innovation in Construction	https://cibworld.org/about-cib/	Event –Publication of conference proceedings (ISARC 2022)
Building Digital Twin Association	https://buildingdigitaltwin.org/	Event –ASHVIN Keynote (BDTIC 2021)
AEICE Cluster Habitat Efficiente (Spain)	www.aeice.org/	Event – BIMTecnica workshop
Sustainable Places	www.sustainableplaces.eu/	Event – workshop hosting (2021 & 2022)
IABMAS – International association for bridge maintenance and safety	https://iabmas.w.waseda.jp/	- Involvement in TC Bridge Load testing - Publication of conference proceedings (IABMAS 2022)
CMM - Associação Portuguesa de Construção Metálica e Mista, Portugal	www.cmm.pt	Event – Keynote presentation (at XIII Conference on Steel and Composite Construction 2021)

2.6 Sister Projects Cluster and related EU projects

The related European research and innovation projects working on Digital Building Twins or digital transformation of the building industry were involved in the ASHVIN thanks to

established synergies in the projects’ communication and dissemination. In total, our project collaborated with 13 related EU projects, as shown in Figure 6 and detailed further in Table 6.

Figure 6 Engaged European Projects

Table 6 List of engaged European projects.

Project Name	Link	ASHVIN’s Contribution
SEISMEC	www.linkedin.com/company/seismec/	Synergies for outreach activities, joint event (February 2024).
OLGA	https://www.olga-project.eu/	Event - keynote presentation (at the OLGA Conference 2023).
StandICT.eu	https://standict.eu/	MoU to foster standardisation in Digital Twins.
ReIncarnate	www.reincarnate-project.eu	Synergies for outreach activities.
HumanTech	https://humantech-horizon.eu/	Synergies for outreach activities.
COGITO	https://cogito-project.eu/	Digital Building Twin Sister Projects Cluster (networking, workshops & newsletters)
BIM2TWIN	https://bim2twin.eu/	
BIMProve	www.bimprove-h2020.eu	
BIMSpeed	www.bim-speed.eu	Event - networking & a joint workshop (BDTIC2023).
BIM4ren	https://bim4ren.eu/	Event – networking & a joint workshop (BDTIC2023).
BIMERR	https://bimerr.eu/	Event – hosting a joint workshop (BDTIC2023).
BIM4EEB	www.bim4eeb-project.eu/	

SPHERE	https://sphere-project.eu/
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2.7 Advisory Board

The advisory board, composed of **6 renowned experts** (see Figure 7) working with transformation of the Construction sector, followed the ASHVIN’s progress throughout the project with the central aim to provide the partners feedback and insights from the industry, which helped to ensure that the ASHVIN research is taking the direct direction. These experts’ profiles are detailed in Table 7

Figure 7 ASHVIN's Advisory Board

Table 7 ASHVIN Advisory Board Members

Name	Title	Affiliation	Type	Country
Mathieu Boda	Business Development	CERVVAL	Industry (Technological)	France
Dr. H. Sebnem Düzgün	Professor	Colorado School of Mines	University	USA
Prof. Heng Li	Chair Professor of Construction Informatics	Hong Kong Polytechnic University	University	Hong Kong
Prof. Martin Fischer	Director, Center for Integrated Facility Engineering - CIFE	Stanford University	University	USA
Prof. Carl Haas	Chair of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering	University of Waterloo	University	Canada
Ms. Salla	Director of Transformation	OAC	Industry	USA

Eckhardt	Services		(Techological)
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During the last project half, **we hosted three online meetings with the advisory board** members enabling to showcase the project's achievements and to ask for their further recommendations.

- In the end of 2022, the partners conducted [a series of one-to-one meetings](#) with the available advisory board members. The aim was to collect insights and recommendations for the final project year.
- On the 6th of February 2023, the ASHVIN standardisation leader presented the project's progress in contributing to the international standardisation in digital twins. This [standardisation workshop](#) was one of the milestones related to WP6 efforts.
- On the 22nd of February 2024, the ASHVIN team called the advisory board for [a final meeting](#) to showcase the develop ASHVIN technologies. Especially, the digital twin platform and the ASHVIN toolkit were demonstrated with short videos, and the AB members encouraged to share these with a varied range of industry stakeholders to showcase the concrete innovations in ASHVIN. This meeting was recorded for the absent members of the group, and their feedback was collected with a final online survey.

Finally, the next sections (Section 3 and 4) describe more in details to type of communication and dissemination activities that the stakeholders were addressed to.

3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The ASHVIN communication and dissemination strategies were developed at the start of the project, and their activities were carried out over 42 project months. These initial strategies have been the redline for all produced communications and for dissemination activities. Our communication focused on raising awareness of the project’s research activities, results, and more general digital twin technologies, whereas the continuous dissemination targeted to spread the project’s tangible results (such as scientific publications, deliverables, university lectures etc.) for the use of the target stakeholders.

The ASHVIN Deliverable 8.2 “Dissemination and Communication Interim Report”⁴ offered an overview of the dissemination and communication strategies in the mid-term of the project. Now, as mentioned in the introduction, this report focuses on the strategy implemented and results achieved during the final half of the project from M19 (April 2022) until M42 (March 2024). However, when assessing the achieved key performance indicators (KPIs), the results from the entire project duration are counted.

To assess the progress and alignment with the fixed objectives of the dissemination and communication strategies, we monitored continuously the achieved KPIs (as they were defined in the project’s grant agreement). Table 8 lists these KPI objectives and assess of these were met at the end of the project; and it can be observed that all the objectives were met, and even beyond.

Table 8 Communication and Dissemination KPIs of the project

	Activity	GA Objective	Achieved In total
Publications	Peer-reviewed scientific research publications in international journals in open-access	10	7
	Peer-reviewed publications and presentations in international conferences in open-access	10	12
	Scientific and Technical Publications (e.g. articles, blog posts) (yearly)	20+	110
Events	No. of scientific events participated	30+	45
	No. of non-scientific events participated	7+	13
Project Website	No. of visitors (monthly average) (users)	1000+	310
	No; of sessions (monthly average)		456
Printed Material	No. of hard copies (e.g. flyers) distributed	2000+	830
Videos	No. of produced videos	3	21
	No of visits (by the end of the project)	3000+	2919
Social Media	Size of the online community (by the end of the project)	3000+	3166
	No. of impressions (monthly average)	500+	11,687
Newsletter	No. of newsletters contributed / released	9	11

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/6405239>

3.1 Overall goals of implementing the strategy M18 – M42

As framed in the previous linked deliverables (D8.1 and D8.2), the communication and dissemination strategies run in three phases corresponding to the project’s progress and timeline. This last reporting report, from April 2022 until March 2024, covered the final phases of these strategies dedicated to targeted communication and to embracing the dissemination.

Figure 8 ASHVIN D&C Strategies M19 - M42

3.2 Updated printed or digital outreach material

Promotion materials include flyers, banners, and brochures all following the project’s branding. These are used especially in events to attract participants attention. New promotion materials were designed upon the requests and needs of the ASHVIN partners, and these included notably:

- **ASHVIN Marketing One Pager**⁵ about the Open Call to onboard new projects to the Digital Twin platform.
- **ASHVIN Marketing Brochure**⁶ showcasing the developed system and its offering for the construction projects.

⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/7777391>

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/7763246>

- **Specific banners** for all communication campaigns that were used for the website publications and featured in the social media posts.

Figure 9 ASHVIN Marketing Brochure for Open Call Promotion

Create a Digital Twin of Your Construction site

?

Do you already use sensor devices to collect data from your site but miss the integration within an internet of things (IoT) platform (internet-driven platform)?

Are you interested in implementing sensor-based monitoring?

If yes, onboard the ASHVIN digital twin platform now! FREE OF CHARGE

With ASHVIN, you can analyze, get insights and make visualisations from data that you have already collected. If you do not collect data yet, the ASHVIN experts can deploy sensors on your site and utilise this data. All of this, **FREE OF CHARGE**, as a part of our research & innovation project.

4 ACHIEVED DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The dissemination activities spread the knowledge and the research results from the project towards the identified target stakeholders. The central aim was to make the results available in open access, feature them as a part of the communication strategy and, this way, ensure that these can be used in innovation and research in digitalisation of the construction project, beyond the ASHVIN framework. As shown in Figure 10, thoroughly, the dissemination activities consisted of **19 scientific publications in open access**, **38 public deliverables**, promotion of **results in open access**, as well as representation of the project across **59 international events** related to the research topics.

Figure 10 Overview of ASHVIN's Dissemination Activities

The next sections will detail the dissemination activities carried out by the entire consortium since the interim review (in March 2022).

4.1 Research in Open Access

In line with the requirement from the European Commission, the project will publish most of its results in open access for the benefit of the European research community and other interested stakeholders. The sharing of the research results has been done in international and European events, via scientific publications in conferences and journals as well as with publication of a set of public deliverables from the project.

ASHVIN has shared over 60 public documents via its open repository and these count in **total 3200+ downloads**. This repository is very useful to track the impact of the published documents, as it allows to monitor the number of views and downloads for each uploaded item.

Figure 11 ASHVIN Community on Zenodo

The following table lists, starting from our most recent item, all the public project items from **the ASHVIN Zenodo Library**⁷. As a reference, Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository and its researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. The ASHVIN project has used Zenodo throughout the project has a central point to access its research results, and the final deliverables due in M42 will be added there (after the submission of this report).

The annexed document to this deliverable (Annex 4 – List of the openly accessible project results on Zenodo) lists all documents added to the project’s online repository.

4.2 Scientific publications in peer-reviewed conferences and journals

In total, the ASHVIN team has published **19 scientific publications** that are all in open access.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ashvin2020>

From these publications, **12 are research papers published in scientific conferences** presenting the ASHVIN research work results, and all these peer-reviewed papers are openly accessible via the ASHVIN Zenodo repository as shown in the previous section. The table in accessible in the annexed documents (Annex 1 – Publications in Scientific Conferences) provides more detailed information about each conference publication, precisizing the title, authors, related conference title, publication date, DOI and link to the publication in open access.

Figure 12 Publication at the EG ICE 2023 Conference Proceedings

7 publications in scientific and peer-reviewed journals and that are openly accessible. The annexed documents of this deliverable (Annex 2 - List Publications in Scientific Journals) provides more detailed information about each conference publication, precisizing the title, authors, related journal title, publication date, DOI and link to the publication in open access. Moreover, at the moment of writing this report, **four additional publications in scientific journals** were submitted and in the process of the journal’s review.

Figure 13 Scientific publication in the journal of engineering

In addition, partners presented their research in **6 additional publications for a journal and conference proceedings, but these are not open accessible, and hence not counted in the key performance indicators (KPIs) as defined by the project’s grant agreement (article 29.2 Open access to scientific publications)**. These publications are presented in Annex 3 - List of related scientific publications with a restricted access. The project’s communication also promoted these results, valuing the contribution to these international academic events especially for stakeholders that participate in the same conferences.

Figure 14 Example of communication banner about participated events

4.3 Public project deliverables

The ASHVIN workplan, managed by TUB under WP9 project management, included a set of **37 public deliverables** that were all disseminated in the ASHVIN communication channels including dedicated blog articles, social media posts and webinars.

Figure 15 Example of a visual banner announcing a public deliverable.

The following table lists the public deliverables that were submitted to the European Commission before M42 (March 2024) (the remaining public deliverables to be submitted in M42 will be added to the list) and that were disseminated in the ASHVIN communication channels throughout the project.

Table 9 List of public ASHVIN deliverables

Title	Link
Deliverable 6.6 Availability Of Measured Maintenance Data Of Infrastructure For Public Domain	https://zenodo.org/records/10351476
D4.6 Visualizing and dashboarding construction activities based on digital twin data	https://zenodo.org/record/8314556
Deliverable 4.4 Risk Management	https://zenodo.org/record/8074932
Deliverable 5.3 A set of KPIs to plan a safe risk-based maintenance	https://zenodo.org/record/7928412
Deliverable 5.2 " Digital-Twin Enabled multi-physics simulation and model matching"	https://zenodo.org/record/7928384
D3.2 Digital Twin-based Geo-Monitoring	https://zenodo.org/record/7794442
D2.3: Parametric design to optimize productivity, resource efficiency, and safety	https://zenodo.org/record/7794389
D4.3 Digital Twin supported lean project planning, control and risk management	https://zenodo.org/record/7313175
D2.2 Evaluation and recommendations for evidence-based design for productivity, resource efficiency, and safety based on historical digital twin data	https://zenodo.org/record/7234679
D4.5 Virtual Commissioning Model	https://zenodo.org/record/7220249
D3.3 Data Fusion Methods and Digital Twin-based IoT Data Processing Pipelines	https://zenodo.org/record/7220164
D4.2 Discrete Event Simulation Formalism for Productive, Resource Efficient, and Safe Construction Planning	https://zenodo.org/record/7220125

D3.1 Visual Analysis for Real Sensing	https://zenodo.org/record/7220100
D1.4 Digital Twin Interoperability in the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220073
D1.5 Safety and Privacy for Digital Twins in the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220040
D1.2 An Ontology for Digital Twin Models for the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220000
D8.3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND EXPLOITATION INTERIM REPORT	https://zenodo.org/record/6405241
D8.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION INTERIM REPORT	https://zenodo.org/record/6405239
D5.1 SHM DIGITAL TWIN REQUIREMENTS FOR RESIDENTIAL, INDUSTRIAL BUILDINGS AND BRIDGES	https://zenodo.org/record/6405220
D7.1 ASHVIN TECHNOLOGY DEMONSTRATION PLAN	https://zenodo.org/record/5542985
D4.1 A SET OF KPIS TO PLAN AND MONITOR PRODUCTIVE, RESOURCE EFFICIENT, AND SAFE CONSTRUCTON SITES	https://zenodo.org/record/5542981
D2.1 A SET OF KPIS TO DESIGN FOR PRODUCTIVITY, RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, AND SAFETY	https://zenodo.org/record/5542975
D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan	https://zenodo.org/record/4299022
D1.1 Launch Version of ASHVIN Platform	https://zenodo.org/record/4556836
D6.1 STANDARDIZATION PLAN	https://zenodo.org/record/4707097

4.4 Participation in Events

During the entire duration of the ASHVIN project, the partners represented the ASHVIN results in **59 international events** related to construction sector and maintenance of civil engineering assets with the support of digital tools. These were either scientific events where partners published scientific conference proceedings related to their research in ASHVIN, or non-scientific events that gathered stakeholders from the construction sector for sharing networks and information. Most of this participation (45 events, including 5 workshops) took place during the last half of the project (from April 2022 onwards) as the work in the project progressed.

Moreover, all participations were showcased on the ASHVIN communication channels with dedicated blog articles and visual banners. The ASHVIN website “knowledge hub” page⁸ featured a category of “events” where one can find all blog articles about the event participations.

Figure 16 ASHVIN website's knowledge hub on events

4.4.1 Scientific events M19 – M42

The project records **29 participation moments in scientific events** during the 2nd project term. These events helped to present the research results and methodology to target stakeholders, especially to academic and scientific communities but also to end-users (i.e., construction project or infrastructure asset managers). In these events, the ASHVIN partners gave **keynote presentations, lectures, seminars, and shared scientific conference proceedings** all related to their work in the project. These were also a great opportunity to connect with stakeholders, and to exchange feedback with related initiatives.

⁸ <https://www.ashvin.eu/blogs/>

Figure 17 INRAPLAN Presentation at OLGA Conference, December 2023

“This participation in the EUROSTRUCT Conference 2023 in Vienna was super successful, and I am very proud to be part of the EUROSTRUCT team!”

Irina Stipanovic
PhD, C.E
Infra Plan consulting, Zagreb, Croatia

Figure 18 INFRAPLAN at Eurostruct 2023

Figure 19 Scientific publication presented at the 31st IGLC Conference 2023

Table 10 provides further information from each participated scientific events, with its' date, name, description, location, and link to the drafted article about it.

Table 10 List of participated scientific events since M19

Date	Title & Link to the related blog article	Partner in charge	Description	Location
27/02/2024	the SEISMEC project symposium	EUR, CERTH, INFRA	Sharing lessons learnt from ASHVIN during the symposium.	Physical, Rotterdam/ Netherlands
29/01/2024	30th International Conference on Multimedia Modeling	CERTH	Publication in the conference: A framework for 3D modelling of construction, sites using aerial imagery and semantic NeRFs (CERTH)	Physical, Amsterdam/ Netherlands
07/01/2024	Washington Transport Research Board annual meeting 2024	INFCON	Presentation of research done for the demo site #3 Airport runway in Croatia, and publication in a book of abstracts.	Physical, Washington / US
13/12/2023	OLGA Conference shaping Green Airports and Smart Cities	INFCON	Keynote speech about the demo site #3 research	Physical, Zagreb, Croatia
12/12/2023	ASHVIN Seminar at TONGJI SEM Business School in Shanghai, China	TUB	TUB was invited to present the ASHVIN project's research and innovation in digital building twins at TONGJI SEM Business School in Shanghai, China. The event was hybrid, counting in total 60 participants	Shanghai, China

03/11/2023	ASHVIN Seminar Hosted at Texas A&M University For Students And Faculty	TUB	The scientific coordinator of the ASHVIN project from the Technical University of Berlin, hosted an academic seminar presenting our research and innovation in the ASHVIN project to students and faculty members of Texas A&M University (United States)	Physical, Texas / United States
30/11/2023	Keynote lecture at ICTWS2023 about "Encompassing Measurements, Advanced Analysis and BIM for Digital Twinning of Steel Structures"	UPC	UPC gave keynote lecture at ICTWS2023, an international conference dedicated to Thin-walled structures.	Physical, Sydney / Australia
23/11/2023	Seminar at the Centre for Spatial Data Infrastructures & Land Administration of the University of Melbourne	UPC	UPC hosted a seminar called "Digital Twins in Practice. Lessons learned, insights and innovations from twinning 15 varied European infrastructure systems". This seminar included a detailed presentation of four major ASHVIN demo cases.	Physical, Melbourne / Australia
27/09/2023	Eurostruct	UPC	UPC and INFRAPLAN represented ASHVIN and two co-authored scientific publications at the Eurostruct Conference 2023.	Physical / Vienna / Austria
12/09/2023	Eurosteel	UPC	UPC presented a conference publication shared the research results on I-Twin, that is one of the outcomes of the different methodologies and technological enablers developed within ASHVIN project.	Physical / Amsterdam / Netherlands
04/07/2023	EG ICE 2023	TUB	TUB presented a publication "Discrete Event Simulation Tool for Productive, Resource-Efficient, and Safe Construction Management".	Virtual participation/ London/ UK
02/07/2023	31st IGLC Conference	TUB	TUB presented a scientific conference proceeding entitled "A combined Digital Twin and Location-Based Management System".	Physical / Lille, France
23/06/2023	EPO Conference	TUB	TUB gave a presentation entitled "Construction Knowledge: Emergent Insights from tacit knowledge experiences".	Physical/ Berlin, Germany
24/05/2023	Computational Civil Engineering (CCE) 2023	AEG	AEG have a presentation about how the ASHVIN digital twin platform and toolkit could improve the construction process for the 30 participants.	Physical / Iasi, Romania
08/05/2023	Guest lecture at a Master class at the Technical University of Iasi	AEG	AEG gave a guest lecture about the ASHVIN system for a master class at the technical university of Iasi.	Physical / Iasi, Romania

17/04/2023	Seminar about ASHVIN at the College of Engineering, University of Notre Dame, US	UPC	UPC hosted a seminar to engineering students discussing the research at the 10 ASHVIN demo sites.	Physical / Indiana, USA
12/04/2023	NASCC The Steel Construction	UPC	UPC published a conferenced paper entitled " "Seasonal analysis of a 846 long steel box girder bridge using Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS) and FE-models". This paper is related to the research at the ASHVIN demonstration site #7 "Bridges in highway network in Spain.	Physical/ Charlotte/USA.
09/01/2023	29th International Conference on Multimedia Modeling	CERTH	CERTH gave a poster presentation entitled "Low-light image enhancement based on U-Net and Haasé.	Bergen, Sweden
13/12/2022	Winter Simulation Conference 2022	TUB	TUB published a paper entitled "Real-Time Activity Duration Extraction of Crane Works for Data-Driven Discrete Event Simulation", authored by several ASHVIN partners (Physical / Singapore
23/09/2022	Contextual Integrity Symposium at Cornell University	EUR	EUR presented ASHVIN and its research on privacy with a presentation entitled "Towards a Privacy Ensuring Digitalized Construction Site"	Physical (New York, US)
14/09/2022	19th International Conference on Content-based Multimedia Indexing	CERTH	CERTH presented a publication in conference proceedings entitled "A survey for image based methods in construction: from images to digital twins."	Physical (Graz, Austria)
27/09/2022	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures 2022	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Towards the digital twinning of a steel plated bridge for maintenance purposes. Case study in Barcelona area".	Physical (Aveiro, Portugal)
14/09/2022	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures (ICSS 2022)	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Geometrical digital twinning of a tapered, horizontally curved composite box girder bridge".	Physical (Aveiro, Portugal)
14/09/2022	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures (ICSS 2022)	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Automated pipeline for the analysis of a scale-reduced steel cable net".	Physical (Aveiro, Portugal)
14/07/2022	ISARC 2022 International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Closing the gap between concrete maturity monitoring and nonlinear time-dependent fem analysis through a digital twin. Case study: post-tensioned concrete slab of an office building, Barcelona, Spain".	Physical (Bogota, Colombia)
14/07/2022	ISARC 2022 International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Towards automated pipelines for processing load test data on a hs railway bridge in Spain using a digital twin".	Physical (Bogota, Colombia)

11/07/2022	<u>International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management 2022</u>	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "On the digital twinning of load tests in railway bridges. Case Study: High Speed Railway Network, Extremadura, Spain".	Physical (Barcelona, Spain)
12/07/2022	<u>International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management 2022</u>	UPC	UPC presented a publication entitled "Ground-Based Interferometer radars for load tests of long-span arch bridges. Case study: Almonte and El Tajo Viaducts, Extremadura, Spain".	Physical (Barcelona, Spain)
07/07/2022	<u>EG-ICE 2022</u>	DTT	DTT gave a presentation showcasing the research of the ASHVIN project entitled "Platology: A A Digital Twin Ontology Suite for the Complete Lifecycle of Infrastructure"	Physical (Aarhus, Denmark)

4.4.2 Non-scientific events M19 – M42

During this reporting period, ASHVIN has been presented or represented in **11 non-scientific events** in Europe. In these events, the partners hosted workshops and gave presentations about the ASHVIN results or conducted networking with different stakeholders to grow the ASHVIN community.

Figure 20 CERTH Team at the Greek Technology Forum in September 2022

Figure 21 UPC Presentation at Think WIoT Days, Online, February 2023

Figure 22 ASHVIN at ECTP Conference 2024

The following table lists all the non-scientific event participations, gives a short description of each event, and provides a link to the related blog article posted on the project's communication channels.

Table 11 Participation in non-scientific events since M19 (April 2022)

Date (deadline)	Title	Partner in charge	Description	Location (Physical/Online)	Link to the related article
06/03/2024	ECTP Conference 2024	NCC	Short presentation about the ASHVIN overall goals and last steps.	Physical, Brussels, Belgium	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/12/ashvin-represented-at-the-ectp-conference-2024-two-decades-shaping-smart-and-green-building/
18/6/2023	Long Night of Science in Berlin	TUB	Joan Evelyn Ongodia & Manuel Jungmann (TUB) presented the ASHVIN for public.	Physical/ Berlin, Germany	www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/21/ashvin-goes-local-participation-to-long-night-of-science-in-berlin/
25/5/2023	Construmat	UPC	Congress speech about: "ASHVIN, a digital platform to improve the productivity of the European construction industry".	Physical / Barcelona, Spain	www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/30/the-ashvin-project-was-featured-in-a-panel-at-the-construmat-event-in-barcelona/
18/5/2023	BuildingSmart Poland	FAS	ASHVIN project represented for networking.	Physical / Poland	www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/25/ashvin-attended-the-buildingsmarts-first-conference-in-poland/
24/03/2023	SmartBuilt4EU Final Conference	AUS	Participation for stakeholder engagement of HorizonEurope projects.	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/03/24/ashvin-attended-the-smartbuilt4eu-project-final-conference/
22/02/2023	Think WIOT Day – Logistics and Construction	UPC	Online lecture given about the Demo Site #1 research.	Online	http://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/24/ashvin-innovation-presented-at-livestream-of-think-wireless-iot-days/
27/10/2022	Spanish Construction Technology Platform At the School of Industrial Engineers of The Technical University of Madrid	UPC	The theme of the day was "Digitalization of roads and railways". Presentation : Demonstration Site 7: Actuaciones Scan-to-BIM para la gemelización digital de un puentes mixtos de carretera.	Physical / Madrid/ Spain	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/27/ashvin-at-the-jornada-de-digitalizacion-de-infraestructuras-lineales-madrid/
21/10/2022	The Disctric Show	DTT	Contribution to a panel discussion on "Digital Twin as a business opportunity for whole analogic assets.	Physical /Barcelona/ Spain	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/24/ashvin-represented-in-panel-discussions-about-digital-twins-as-business-opportunity-at-the-the-district-show/
11/10/2022	IAMBAS Technical Committee Meeting	UPC	Representation of the project in a Technical Committee on load tests of bridges (DEMO 1).	Online	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/11/ashvin-joins-the-iabmas-technical-meeting-to-present-demo-site-1-results/
29/9/2022	Greek Technology Forum	CERTH	Forum, ASHVIN poster exhibited.	Thessaloniki, Greece	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/06/ashvin-presented-at-the-9th-greek-technology-forum-in-thessaloniki/

26/05/2022	BDTIC 2022	DTT	Presentation about the ASHVIN's achievements.	Online	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/05/19/ashvin-project-at-bdtic-2021/
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4.5 Workshops

During the reporting period, the **ASHVIN team organised or co-hosted five workshops**. These sessions were conducted by ASHVIN-team members and involved international stakeholders across the globe. These sessions (listed in Table 12) were a great opportunity to present the ASHVIN innovations and to exchange ideas with the workshop participants.

Figure 23 AEGMatters hosted a workshop at the BIMCOM Summit 2023

Figure 24 UPC hosted a workshop session at the Digital Sciences Initiative of the University of Sydney in Australia

Figure 25 TUB hosted a workshop at CONVR 2022 Conference

Table 12 List of ASHVIN's Workshops

Date (deadline)	Title	Partner in charge	Description	Location (Physical/Online)	Link to the related article
27/11/2023	Workshop session at the Digital Sciences Initiative of the University of Sydney	UPC	UPC hosted a workshop session introducing the participants to using very simple digital twin technologies to educators with the aim of fostering potential digital initiatives for their own courses.	Physical, Sydney / Australia	www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/09/contribution-of-ashvin-for-educational-activities-oceaniameetsashvin/
25 - 26/10/2023	5th edition of the BIMcon Summit in Romania	DigitAEC	Dr. Ungureanu conducted a workshop entitled "Digital twins for the execution stage".	Physical / Iasi, Romania	www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/09/ashvin-participates-in-the-5th-edition-of-the-bimcon-summit-in-romania/
03/05/2023	Joint Workshop entitled "Ontologies and Linked Data in the AECO domain" at BDTIC 2023	AEG	Joint workshop "Ontologies and Linked Data in the AECO domain" with several sister projects, including: BIM4REN, BIM-SPEED, BIMERR, BIM4EEB, SPHERE, BIMProve, BIM2TWIN, ASHVIN and COGITO.	Physical / Antwerp, Belgium	www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/09/ashvin-participates-in-the-bdtic-international-congress-in-antwerp/
16/11/2022	Digital Twin Workshop at CONVR 22 Conference	TUB	TUB gave a keynote presentation entitled "Engineering the natural and built environment: From today's knowledge into future visions". Also, in line with the main topic, Prof. Hartmann presented ASHVIN in a dedicated workshop focused on deploying digital twin in	Physical / Seoul / Korea	www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/21/ashvin-presented-at-the-convr-22-conference-in-south-korea/

			construction projects.		
07/09/2022	Sustainable Places (SP2022)	TUB	The ASHVIN team hosted a joint workshop at joint workshop co-organized by the Building Digital Twin Association (BDTA) and 6 EU-funded projects, resulting a paper: Ontologies in Digital Twin. Methodology, lessons learned and practical approach.	Physical (Nizza, France)	www.ashvin.eu/2022/09/13/ashvin-project-presented-at-sustainable-places-conference-2022/

5 PERFORMED COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The communication around the ASHVIN project focused on raising the awareness of the project activities and results among the target public. This final term of the project centred its actions on targeted communication publishing targeted articles about the ASHVIN innovation, its benefits to the construction sector and creating specialised communication materials, including essentially focused content, videos, and podcasts. Figure 26 provides the overview of the deployed communication channels and their overall impact on the ASHVIN communication strategy.

Figure 26 Overview of ASHVIN's Communication Activities

In terms of communication content, we focused on the key axes, including project facts and proactive campaigns that offered opportunities for interaction with the target audience. As shown in Figure 27, the project facts content shared updated related to deliverables, scientific publications, ASHVIN demonstration sites, featured events and the technical innovation; whereas the proactive campaigns treated related international and European topics, the ASHVIN research team, the ASHVIN Open Call, the project meetings and webinars, as well as stakeholders’ engagement.

Figure 27 Overview of ASHVIN's Communication Content Categories

The communication channels and content are presented in more detail in the next sections, with focus on the achieved results and impact.

5.1 Website

5.1.1 Website updates

The ASHVIN website⁹ remained one of the key gateways to the project’s communication.

During this reporting period, we continued to update the project website regularly; essentially, the “knowledge hub”-page¹⁰ that counted several new blog articles each month. And the produced ASHVIN tool tutorials were added on the “digital toolkit”-page¹¹ (under each relevant digital twin tool). Finally, to showcase better the cluster project, a new page dedicated to “Collaborations” was added to the website.

The website directs users to the ASHVIN’s social media channels and provides the contact email (contact@ashvin.eu) for any further information.

⁹ <https://www.ashvin.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.ashvin.eu/blogs/>

¹¹ <https://www.ashvin.eu/digital-toolkit/>

Figure 28 A view from the ASHVIN Website

5.1.2 Website traffic

In average, **310 monthly users visit the ASHVIN website** (based on data from Google Analytics 4 tool), which would imply that in total the website has received **over 13.000 visitors** during its lifetime. Based on a sample of data from April 2023 until February 2024 from Google Analytics 4, we can see that the top-5 visiting user countries are Germany, United States, India, Spain, and Netherlands. In addition, after the main landing page, the knowledge hub-page and ASHVIN toolkit page score among the most visited ones on the website.

Figure 29 Information on the ASHVIN website users between April 2023 and February 2024

The website page will be updated beyond the project ending, with results especially in the form of public deliverables. This will also stay live two years after the project completion.

5.2 Knowledge publications

In this second part of the project, we focused on developing and contributing to focused publications to the target stakeholders. These knowledge publications included new blog articles that were released either weekly or monthly, based on the achievements, as well as publications in external media outlets and external information platforms.

5.2.1 Blog articles

These publications are part of the communication strategy, and they aim to inform the stakeholders timely about ASHVIN’s ongoing activities, achievements, and opportunities. During the second project half (since April 2022), in 24 project months, **we produced and published over 100 blog articles** dedicated to the ASHVIN systems and the project’s activities and results. These articles were featured with related social media posts, and sometimes even audiovisual content (either podcast series or videos).

Figure 30 Example of a recent blog article

Annex 5 provides the complete list of the ASHVIN blog articles produced during this reporting period.

5.2.2 Earned articles in external media

The ASHVIN project was featured in **four articles published** in a Spanish journal, in a book in Catalan, in a scientific publication and a Spanish digital platform, as further described in the following table.

Table 13 ASHVIN apparitions on external media

Date	Title	Short description	Hyperlink
19/02/2024	Cervells, robots, humans: apunts d'un UPCnauta	The research from the project was used as a source of information in a book published in Catalan by the ASHVIN partner, UPC.	https://upcommons.upc.edu/handle/2117/400528
29/05/2023	Bessons’ digitals perquè no caiguin els ponts (Related to Demo Sites #1 & #8 Maintenance and Digital Birth of Bridges)	Ara Emprenem Media , the most widely read Catalan-language daily in its digital edition, released a digital and printed version of an article discussing the use of digital twins in construction to enhance design and maintenance. The focus was on the ASHVIN project's demonstrator #7, Bridges, in the highway network of Castellbisbal, Catalonia, Spain. Notably, Ara Emprenem was the only publication among Barcelona and Madrid titles that saw growth in its print edition.	https://www.upc.edu/ca/sala-de-premsa/als-mitjans/pdf/2023-05-28-ara-bessons-digitals-perque-no-caiguin-els-ponts
23/06/2023	Analysis of Digital Twins in the Construction Industry: Current Trends and Applications	This is a scientific publication external to the ASHVIN project featuring ASHVIN as one of modern applications for digital twin in construction.	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371267370_Analysis_of_Digital_Twins_in_the_Construction_Industry_Current_Trends_and_Appli

<p>23/06/2023</p>	<p>El proyecto Ashvin ofrecerá una plataforma de gemelo digital de código abierto que integra IoT y tecnología de imagen</p>	<p>Casadomo is a Spanish digital platform communication about intelligent digital solutions of tomorrow.</p>	<p>https://www.casadomo.com/2023/06/23/proyecto-ashvin-ofrecera-plataforma-gemelo-digital-codigo-abierto-integra-iot-tecnologia-imagen</p>
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Figure 31 Paper Journal article published about ASHVIN demo sites in Spain

5.2.3 Publications in external platforms

Throughout the project, ASHVIN was featured in 22 different partners' and external stakeholders' communication channels, amplifying its research and innovation developments, advancements, and opportunities.

The publications of the first two years mainly come from the consortium. On one hand, the articles published by partners Mainflux Labs and the Polytechnic University of Catalonia explain the project and their participation as members of the consortium, stating that "[Mainflux Labs is a Member of the Construction R&D Project Funded by the EU H2020 Program](#)" and "[Digital Twins con Aplicación en el Sector de la Construcción](#)".

There is a section dedicated to ASHVIN at partners' [DT](#), [CERTH](#), [FAS](#), [INGEO](#), [Plan B](#), [Infra](#) and [TUB](#) websites. Additionally, the Project Coordinator, Timo Hartmann, wrote a blog

article on ASHVIN titled "[Modelling, abstraction, and digital twins](#)", which explains the baseline of the ASHVIN project. Among the external stakeholders, [Laia Associates](#) (Landscape Architecture Investigation and Applications), the [ECTP organisation featured the project](#), [development aid](#) and the [Information Technologies Institute](#) presented ASHVIN on their websites.

In the third year of the ASHVIN project, more external stakeholders started to spread the word about its research, innovations, and opportunities. The SmartBuilt4EU Project published a brochure highlighting 100 Smart Buildings projects and 37 promising innovations and ASHVIN was among them - "[Real-time as-built vs as-designed comparison](#)." An engaged consortium member, the Polytechnic University of Catalonia, also featured ASHVIN in a podcast episode called "[Els bessons digitals](#)." Moreover, ASHVIN's blog article, "[ASHVIN's Digital Innovation based on Digital Twins Boosts the European Construction Industry](#)," was featured on Construo, the leading collaborative platform and marketplace for the construction industry. Regarding standardization plan, the deliverable was shared in a [blog article](#) on the EUOS (EU Observatory for ICT Standardization powered by StandICT.eu).

- Energy efficiency
- Maintenance & fault prediction
- Comfort
- Convenience
- Health, well-being & accessibility
- Information to occupants
- Energy flexibility & storage

- Website
- Coordinator
- Partners

Start date **Oct. 2020**
 Duration **36 months**
 Status **In Progress**

Total budget **5,6 M€**

ASHVIN

Assistant for Healthy, Safe and Productive Virtual Construction, Design, Operation & Maintenance using Digital Twin

The ASHVIN project develops a solution combining an open-source digital twin platform connected to IoT and image technologies and integrated applications with the objective to reinforce productivity, while reducing costs, and safety of European construction sites and maintenance operations.

The implementation of the system is demonstrated on ten real case studies including bridges, buildings, and industrial projects around Europe.

www.ashvin.eu

TUB, Germany

Austria: ASI
 Croatia: INFCON
 Germany: TUB, DTT, SBP
 Greece: CERTH
 Netherlands: EUR, INGEO
 Poland: FAS
 Serbia: MFL
 Spain: AUS, UPC
 Sweden: NCC, Plan B

Figure 32 ASHVIN featured in the SmartBuilt4EU Catalogue

Furthermore, ASHVIN's events were featured in external communication channels. Webinars #2 and #3 were publicly broadcasted on platforms such as **BUILD-UP** and **EU-AGENDA**. Webinar #2 received 152 views while webinar #3 received 239 views. During the Sustainable Places event 2022, the [workshop](#) about “Ontologies” conducted with sister projects was featured and made available on the YouTube account of the organisers.

5.3 Social media presence

ASHVIN is present on 3 social media networks: LinkedIn, Twitter, and YouTube. With a digital community of **3100+ followers**, **7808 monthly average impressions**, **1.8K posts** and **5.73% engagement rate**, these channels were essential for communicating with stakeholders daily, providing updates on ASHVIN's scientific publications, events, progress on demonstrators and developed technologies. Thanks to them, stakeholders have engaged with ASHVIN's innovations, research, and developments as well as activities, raising awareness campaigns and opportunities such as onboarding the Digital Twin platform and participating in webinars.

5.3.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a relevant channel for connecting with the highest and most impactful target audiences, including the construction industry and DT technology providers. ASHVIN has built a community of **800+ followers** on this social media channel, with **135,000 impressions** and **64,000-page reach**. Additionally, ASHVIN launched a newsletter within the social media channel, providing content within **5 editions** for **289 subscribers** among civil engineers and construction stakeholders.

Based on LinkedIn's Analytics, ASHVIN's top 3 follower demographic job functions are **engineering, research, and education**. The industries most represented in the community are **higher education, civil engineering, research services and construction**. The LinkedIn community mainly comes from **Germany, Greece, and Spain**, countries that are all represented in the ASHVIN project consortium.

ASHVIN's average post engagement rate on this social network is **6.5%**, which demonstrates that the community interacts with the created content and campaigns. The most impactful campaigns showcased the **people behind the project** and **activities engaging with external stakeholders** such as the Advisory Board members, and presentations researchers involved in the project.

ASHVIN 792 followers
6mo · 🌐

🔊 **BREAKING NEWS** 📢

The **#ASHVINTeam** is now in the process of onboarding construction projects!

- ASHVIN's Digital Twin solution comprises a set of 10 smart building applications supporting the design, construction and maintenance of buildings and infrastructure assets.
- This year we open the **#ASHVINPlatform** to more construction and maintenance projects by collecting their data with a wide range of IoT and image technologies through the **#WINASHVIN** initiative.
- Our initial platform onboarding projects are in Poland, Croatia and Spain. The **#ASHVINTeam** has already conducted site visits to install sensors and take measurements. Discover more information about their **#DigitalTwin** experience over Europe in our article 📄

<https://lnkd.in/jecrpFt69>

Interested in onboarding the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform for your construction project?
📧 Send us an email at contact@ashvin.eu

#SmartBuilding #DigitalTransformation #DigitalDecade #DigitalTwin

New Demo Sites Onboard ASHVIN's Digital Twin Platform
ashvin.eu · 3 min read

👍👍👍 35 1 comment · 5 reposts

👍 Like 💬 Comment 🔄 Repost

Organic impressions: 520 Impressions Preview results ▾

ASHVIN Project
792 followers
10mo · 🌐

We recognise the talents behind ASHVIN's innovation in **#DigitalTwins!**
🙌 Thank you, **Rolando Chacón**, for your commitment to digitising and transforming the European Construction sector!

He is WP5 Structural monitoring and asset management coordinator and **#ASHVINDemonstrators 1, 6, 7 and 9 Leader!**

- A polyglot Associate Professor at **Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)**
- 46 journal articles
- 57 presentations of works at congresses.

We recognise his hard work in developing strategies encompassing state-of-the-art instrumentation and control for infrastructures. He is behind our **#digital** twin-based structural monitoring and asset management solutions and **#ASHVINDemonstrators** that establish a real-time connection between physical infrastructures and virtual realistic numerical models.

#PraiseASHVINTeam

Rolando Chacón
Associate Professor
Polytechnical University Catalunya
WP5 Coordinator and Demos 1,6,7 & 9 leader in ASHVIN

👍👍👍 58 2 comments

👍 Like 💬 Comment 🔄 Repost

Organic impressions: 1,136 Impressions Preview results ▾

Figure 33 Examples of successful LinkedIn Posts

ASHVIN Project
792 followers
1yr · 🌐

!! Meet our **#AdvisoryBoard** !!
Get to know **Dr Sebnem Duzgun**, Associate Department Head Full Prof. and Fred Banfield Distinguished Chair in Mining Engineering at **Colorado School of Mines** 🇺🇸

🔬 **Expert and Research** 🔬
👤 Over 20 years of experience in **#MiningEngineering** on mine closure and reclamation, quantitative **#sustainability** assessment for mining projects, **#risk** and **#safety** analysis for coal mines, mine environmental monitoring using **#remote #sensing**, reliability-based design and analysis of rock slopes, uncertainty modelling in rock engineering, and other interdisciplinary topics.

- Specialties 🏆
- More than a hundred publications
- Four book chapters
- Author of the book "Remote Sensing of The Mine Environment"

We thank her for helping us improve our **#ASHVINTools** and guiding our **#HorizonEU** project towards the future **#ConstructionIndustry!**
Meet all the members of our **#AdvisoryBoard** 📄
<https://bit.ly/3QG7iH>
Stay tuned !

👍👍👍 51 1 comment

👍 Like 💬 Comment 🔄 Repost

Organic impressions: 1,299 Impressions Preview results ▾

5.3.2 X (former Twitter)

The X channel represents the most prominent digital ecosystem following the project, with a community of **2,300+ followers**, **71,000 impressions** and an engagement rate of **5.4%**. Through this social media channel, ASHVIN connected with stakeholders from the construction industry, digital transformation advocates, other European-funded projects, and a general audience. The most impactful campaigns were joint activities with our sister projects, as well as the activities (webinars) and opportunities (onboarding the ASHVIN's Digital Twin platform).

Figure 34 Examples of successful posts on X

5.3.3 YouTube

YouTube is a highly effective platform for delivering engaging audiovisual content to audiences. ASHVIN utilized this channel to showcase the DT tools tutorials, demonstrators, and DT platform, along with introducing the team behind the project through campaigns such as #ImpactStories, #InnovationStories (podcast), and #ResearchStories. ASHVIN's YouTube channel has **40 subscribers**, **32 videos**, **78.5 hours of watch time**, and garnered **3,000+ views** (2,500+ from external users). The videos have mainly attracted stakeholders

from Spain, Germany, and Greece. Additionally, ASHVIN's YouTube channel serves as an open repository of audiovisual content, where online webinar sessions are stored.

Figure 35 ASHVIN's Youtube Channel

5.4 Produced Videos

ASHVIN has created and shared **32+ videos**, combining technical content of the project with the team working on the project and their contributions. All videos were published on the ASHVIN YouTube Channel¹², and promoted on the different communication channels. The best ranking videos are the technical contents, specifically demonstrators 6 **“From LIDAR to Digital Twins”** and 2 **“3D Scanning for a Digital Twin”** as well as the **technical webinar 2** related to **infrastructure maintenance**.

Figure 36 Example of a produced video - ASHVIN Demo Site 1¹³

The following table provides details from all published videos, including publication dates, direct access to the videos and number of views.

¹² <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkxYtGHngRgiODx5eb9vibQ>

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8BTwK6iKuzc&t=42s>

Table 14 List of produced videos

Date	Video	Views (in Feb 2024)
20/10/2021	Demo #6: From LIDAR to Digital Twins	441
October 29th, 2021	Demo #2: 3D Scanning for a Digital Twin	267
December 15th, 2021	Demo #9: Sce reduced cable net – Test on sensors and MatchFEM	131
January 21st, 2021	Demosite #5: Kineum building in Sweden	204
December 20th, 2022	ASHIN Demo site 5 #Kineum office building in Sweden	62
December 20th, 2022	#ASHVINTools Tutorial : #BRICS	156
December 20th, 2022	#ASHVINTool Tutorial: #EBD	81
December 20th, 2022	#ASHVINTool Tutorial: #GEN	111
January 16th, 2023	#ASHVINTools Tutorial : #MatchFEM	178
February 28th, 2023	#ASHVIN Technical Webinar on the Digital Twin Platform	148
March 7, 2023	#Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain with #digitaltwin	147
May 23rd, 2023	#ASHVIN Technical Webinar 2	351
June 26th, 2023	#ASHVINStories : General Assembly #6	50
July 5 th , 2023	Digital Twins and risk-based asset management	105
July 13 th , 2023	Digital twin data to create better designs	47
July 20 th , 2023	Public availability of infrastructure data	39
July 27 th , 2023	Digital twins as assistants for infrastructure maintenance	41
August 3 rd , 2023	Digital twins for construction processes	47
August 16 th , 2023	Developing various high-quality conceptual design options effectively	32
September 7 th , 2023	A new process model to control the construction phase	25
October 3 rd , 2023	#ImpactStories : Encompassing data collected with sensors and devices	31
October 17 th , 2023	Digital twin tools for the construction phase	35
November 16th, 2023	Managing the technical developments of ASHVIN	30
November 30, 2023	#ResearchStories : Human factors of ASHVIN	24
November 30, 2023	#ResearchStories : AI-driven methodologies	9
November 30, 2023	#ResearchStories : Maintenance of Buildings and Bridges	7
January 21st, 2024	#ResearchStories :Virtual representation of the multiphysics of an asset	72
January 22nd, 2024	Collecting and using data for efficient construction management	26
January 28th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Computer science abilities	12

February 4th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Conceptual engineering designs	42
February 11th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Integrating and fusing data	5
February 22nd, 2024	#ASHVIN Interactive Webinar 3	20
Views in total		2935

5.5 ASHVIN Podcast Series

ASHVIN launched a podcast called "**Innovation Stories**" on YouTube. The podcast series showcases the technological, technical, and societal innovations that result from the project's research on DT technologies. The **8 available episodes reached 370+ views and 9 hours of watch time**, providing five-minute audio content featuring interviews with the people working on ASHVIN developments.

Figure 37 ASHVIN Innovation Stories Podcast

Each episode starts with a short intro of the ASHVIN project and an outro calling interested stakeholders to onboard the DT platform. Then, the core content of each episode follows with the speaker's introduction, the challenges this person addressed with their innovation, and the innovation itself.

Table 15 Episodes of the ASHVIN Innovation Stories Podcast

Date	Episode	Views
July 5 th 2023	Digital Twins and risk-based asset management	105
July 13 th 2023	Digital twin data to create better designs	47
August 3 rd 2023	Digital twins for construction processes	47
July 27 th 2023	Digital twins as assistants for infrastructure maintenance	41
July 20 th 2023	Public availability of infrastructure data	39
October 17 th 2023	Digital twin tools for the construction phase	35
August 16 th 2023	Developing various high-quality conceptual design options effectively	32
September 7 th 2023	A new process model to control the construction phase	25
Views in total		371

Regarding the promotion, all the episodes were compiled into a website blog article and published on social media channels (LinkedIn and X) through video teasers, carousels, banners, and the project's newsletter.

The screenshot shows a LinkedIn post from the ASHVIN Project, which has 792 followers. The post is dated 4 days ago and features the following content:

- Text:** "Dive into the world of #DigitalTwins in the #ConstructionIndustry with our podcast series #InnovationStories! 🎧🔥"
- Text:** "🔥 What's Inside: Our series uncovers the technological, technical and societal innovations emerging from our research on digital twin technologies. It's not just about the tech - it's about the transformative impact they have on the industry."
- Text:** "🔥 Learn from the Experts: Get insights straight from the brilliant minds at ASHVIN. Discover the challenges they've tackled, the innovative methodologies developed, and how these advancements could revolutionise your approach to construction."
- Text:** "🔥 Listen to [Irina Stipanović](#), [Paul Merz](#), [Joan Evelyn O.](#), [Jason Pridmore](#), [Rahul Tomar](#), [Rogier Jongeling](#) and [Manuel Jungmann](#) committed to fostering a construction industry that's not only safer and more productive but also more sustainable."
- Text:** "Tune in and be part of the change! 📌"
<https://lnkd.in/ek7jHBUJ>
- Hashtags:** #EUFunded #H2020 #DigitalDecade #SmartBuilding #DigitalTransition
- Image:** A promotional banner for the ASHVIN Podcast. It features the ASHVIN logo (a green and blue circular graphic) and the word "ASHVIN" in large blue letters. Below it, the word "PODCAST" is written in white on a dark blue background. A yellow "SOUND ON" button is visible. At the bottom, it says "#INNOVATIONSTORIES" and "Funded by the European Union".
- Text:** "ASHVIN Mini-Podcast Series – Innovation Stories"
ashvin.eu · 1 min read
- Engagement:** Arantxa Echarte and 7 others · 1 repost
- Actions:** Like, Comment, Repost
- Text:** "Be the first to comment on this"
- Text:** "Organic impressions: 383 Impressions" and "Preview results" with a dropdown arrow.

Figure 38 Podcast promotion on social media

A HUMAN TOUCH OF OUR ENDEAVOURS

ASHVIN project has explored digital twins resulting in technological, technical, and societal innovations. **#InnovationStories** and **#ImpactStories** showcase progress and positive impacts. Personal experiences and insights from the project team provide interesting facts about the future of digital twin applications.

Figure 39 Podcast promotion via newsletter

5.6 Newsletters

ASHVIN produced newsletters that complement the email engagement strategy, and these were sent regularly to **364 subscribers**. The newsletters provided updates on the project's main activities, achievements, campaigns, and opportunities for stakeholders. All editions are available on Zenodo, the project's open repository, and have received **1,030+ views** and **410+ downloads**.

Also, the project's newsletters were published in LinkedIn, helping to increase the number of subscribers, and gaining even more visibility. Moreover, ASHVIN was featured in other stakeholders' newsletters, which helped to amplify the project's impact.

5.6.1 ASHVIN newsletters

In total, **8 newsletters** were released through the Mailchimp platform, providing updates to the **78 subscribers**. These issues had as an average **2.2% of open rate** and **12% of unique clicks**. The most impactful newsletter is the one released with sister projects "Joint Flash" (see section 5.6.3). In addition, from Newsletter #5 onwards the newsletters were also spread via **LinkedIn Newsletter tool** counting an additional number of **292 subscribers**.

Figure 40 ASHVIN Newsletter series vol. 1, 2, 3 and 4

Figure 41 ASHVIN Newsletter series vol. 5, 6 and 7

The following table lists the produced newsletters, and recorded opens and clicks from the MailChimp tool (counting 78 subscribers). From newsletter #5 onwards, these were also published on LinkedIn, and these results are not reflected on this table (because the LinkedIn Newsletter tool analytics are different).

Table 16 List of the ASHVIN Newsletters

Newsletter	Date	Opens	Clicks	Views Zenodo	Downloads Zenodo
Vol 1. - Introduction	June 24 th 2021	11	2	114	65
Vol 2. - Digital Toolkit	December 6 th 2021	11	5	96	58
Vol 3.- Deliverables	May 6 th 2022	18	6	100	54
Vol 4.- Deliverables	November 28 th 2022	28	5	175	58
Vol 5. - Open Call	March 7 th 2023	20	7	282	49
Vol 6.- Demonstrators	June 29 th 2023	22	10	45	21
Joint Flash - Sister Projects	August 31 st 2023	40	10	197	96
Vol 7. - Three-year	November 30 th 2023	36	4	19	13
Vol8.	<i>To be published in March 2024</i>				

5.6.2 External newsletters featuring ASHVIN

The impact of stakeholder’ engagement within the ASHVIN’s communication is reflected on the external newsletters featuring the project. The project has gained a dedicated space in the following **9 external newsletters**:

Table 17 List of featured external newsletters

External Newsletter	Date	Featuring
Presentation of ASHVIN Project at UPC newsletter	September 1 st , 2022	Project
Vol. 1 HumanTech	December 19 th 2022	Project
Vol. 1 Reincarnate	December 22 nd 2022	Project

Vol. 1 BIMProve	June 7 th 2021	Project
Vol. 6 BIMProve	March 28 th 2023	Open Call
Vol 4. Reincarnate	January 31 st 2024	Webinar #3
Vol 1. AUSTRALO	December 5 th 2023	Innovation stories
Vol 2. AUSTRALO	January 9 th 2024	Research stories
Vol 3. AUSTRALO	February 13 th 2024	Webinar #3

5.6.3 Cluster projects' Joint Flash newsletters

In the frame of stakeholder collaboration with its sister projects, ASHVIN coordinated releasing a Joint Flash newsletter. The purpose of this newsletter was to present the four projects funded under the same call (BIMProve, Cogito, BIM2TWIN and ASHVIN), the latest news and results on research and innovation developments and the opportunities for industry stakeholders. The two issues of the Joint-Flash newsletters were released in August 2023 (coinciding with the end of the BIMProve project) and March 2024 (at the end of ASHVIN, BIM2Twin and COGITO projects). Every project shared the newsletter in their communication channels (website and social networks), maximising the dissemination and impact of the initiative.

At ASHVIN, we prepared the newsletter layout and content regarding the project and organised the communication campaign. In addition to creating the newsletter, we published a blog article dedicated to the Joint Flash initiative, uploaded it to our open repository and ran a one-month communication campaign to promote it on social networks.

Figure 42 Sister Projects' Joint Flash Newsletter

Newsletter	Date	Opens	Clicks	Views Zenodo	Downloads Zenodo
Joint Flash #1	August 31 st 2023	40	10	197	96
Joint Flash #2	March 2024	<i>To be released during March 2024.</i>			

5.7 Technical Webinars

Webinars are a tool to spread the research results from the project to specific target audiences. The projects hosted a series of three webinars focusing on technical and societal aspects of the deployment of the digital twin technologies in the construction and maintenance projects. In total, these sessions recorded **220 registrations, 137 participations and 520+ views of the recordings.**

The communication campaign was framed with a dedicated communication toolkit including visual banners, the webinar objectives, and agendas as well as information about the target audience. This toolkit served to invite stakeholders to the sessions via the key ASHVIN communication channels, including social media and the website, and partners networks. Also, one-to-one invitations were sent out and relevant external platforms (EU Agenda¹⁴ and EU Built UP¹⁵) shared the event.

Figure 43 EU BuildUP announcement of the Webinar #3

All the webinars were co-organised by several ASHVIN partners offering a floor to the different project partners to stage their research results across the work packages and to gather direct feedback from the stakeholder’s community. Also, the objective was to do short, 1-hour sessions to get participants full attention and to initiate discussions among the participants.

¹⁴ <https://euagenda.eu/events/2024/02/22/ashvin-webinar-3-how-does-access-to-open-data-transform-infrastructure-maintenance>

¹⁵ <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/news-and-events/events/how-does-access-open-data-transform-infrastructure-maintenance>

ASHVIN **Funded by the European Union**

TECHNICAL WEBINAR #2

Maintenance of Civil Engineering Assets with Digital Twin Applications

 Tuesday 23 May 2023
 12:00 - 13:00 CEST

Welcome & Introduction to ASHVIN

What is the ASHVIN solution, and which challenges of the Construction industry does it solve? Ashvin Platform
Rahul Tomar, Technical Coordinator - Digital Twin Technology
12:00 - 12:10

Maintenance of Infrastructure Assets - WP5 Presentation

ASHVIN Tools MATCHFEM, GIS & RISA
Rolando Chacon, WP5 Leader - Polytechnical University of Catalunya
12:10 - 12:20

ASHVIN Demonstrators

#3: Airport infrastructure in Zadar, Croatia
Irina Stipanovic, Demo Site #3 Leader - Infra Plan Consulting
Ilias Koulalis, WP3 Leader - Center for Research & Technology Hellas
12:20 - 12:35

#1: Bridges for high-speed railways in Extremadura, Spain
#7: Bridges in highway network in Barcelona, Spain
Rolando Chacon, WP5 Leader - Polytechnical University of Catalunya
12:35 - 12:50

ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform

How could external stakeholders benefit from it?
ASHVIN Open Call for construction projects
Discussion Q&A & Conclusions
12:50 - 13:00

Moderated by: **Mona Marill, ASHVIN's Communication & Dissemination Leader**
[Register here!](#)

Follow it on our social networks!

Figure 44 Example of an ASHVIN webinar agenda

The first public ASHVIN Technical Webinar, entitled “**Discovering the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform**” was hosted on the 28th of February 2023. This session aimed to showcase the IoT-driven digital twin platform built in the ASHVIN projects towards interested external stakeholders and to motivate new construction projects to onboard the ASHVIN system with their sensor data.

Built on the experience of the first webinar, and hosted on the 23rd of May 2023, the second ASHVIN webinar was a great success, counting 130 registration and 86 participants. This success is certainly related to the webinars attracting topic **“Maintenance of civil engineering asses with digital twin applications”**. This session presented the project’s innovation and results in deploying digital twin tools for the maintenance of civil engineering assets during their entire life cycle.

The third webinar, that took place on the 23rd of February 2024, was dedicated to more societal approach to the deployment of digital twin technologies. It was titled **“How does access to open data transform infrastructure maintenance? Discussions and insights from research findings.”** This interactive webinar delved into the realm of accessing open data for infrastructure maintenance, fostering discussions, insights, and valuable feedback from stakeholders through Slide.

Figure 45 ASHVIN Webinar #3 speaker, Irina Stipanovic from INFRAPLAN

The following table lists the three webinars and they key results in terms of reached audience.

Table 18 ASHVIN Webinars

Title	Date	Registration	Participants	Recording views (via Youtube)
Technical Webinar #1 Discovering the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform	28/02/2023	38	25	149
Technical Webinar #2 Maintenance of civil engineering asses with digital twin applications	23/05/2023	130	86	353
Webinar #3 - Advancing Open Data for Future Infrastructure Maintenance	23/02/2024	52	26	21

Moreover, after each webinar, the participants were asked to fill in an online short questionnaire providing feedback of the session. The collected responses were used as feedback for creating new communication activities.

5.8 Communicating on the project results

Throughout the project, and especially during the last two project years, the major efforts in the project's impact were dedicated to raising the target stakeholders' awareness about the achieved results, including essentially the submitted public deliverables, scientific publications in open access, participations to major events and meetings. All in all, the ASHVIN team's work was carried out transparently, enabling to showcase how the EU-funded project was progressing and which objectives were met and how. We have communicated in total about over 25 scientific publications published in the framework of the project, 38 public deliverables written based on the ASHVIN's research and activities, and 38 scientific or non-scientific events that the ASHVIN partners organised or where they participated representing the project. All these communications included a dedicated article on the ASHVIN website "Knowledge hub"-page¹⁶ as well as related posts on our social media channels.

Figure 46 Example of a banner of a scientific publication

5.9 ASHVIN's Thematic campaigns

In parallel of the continuous communication on the project's tangible results, we worked on **six thematic campaigns** that all focused on specific topics showcasing different aspects related to the project and the digital transformation of construction sector. The aim of these campaigns, that run over months, was to engage with the stakeholders until the end of the

¹⁶ <https://www.ashvin.eu/blogs/>

project and demonstrate from different points of views how digital twin tools can boost the construction industry, its productivity, efficiency, and safety.

Each campaign included a series of blog articles, specific social media strategies and sometimes even produced videos that were all spread across the established communication channels.

Table 19 Summary of the ASHVIN’s thematic communication campaigns

Campaign topic	Scope	Timing
ASHVIN KPI50 Marketing – Onboard the ASHVIN digital twin platform	To find external end-users (e.g., construction sites) who would like to onboard the ASHVIN DT platform.	February – December 2023
European thematic campaigns	To promote the key European thematic in policies and showcase how these are applied in the ASHVIN project.	January – December 2023
ASHVIN tools for the different construction phases	To demonstrated how the ASHVIN system can support the three different phases of the construction projects: design, construction, and maintenance.	September – December 2023
ASHVIN Demonstration Sites	To showcase the performed work and achieved results across the 10 ASHVIN demonstration sites.	October 2022 – January 2024
ASHVIN Impact Stories	To share insights from the ASHVIN team members about the further exploitation of the created solution	September 2023 – March 2024
ASHVIN Research Stories	To showcase the new generation of researchers (from MsC, PhD and Post Doc levels) working behind the ASHVIN project.	January – February 2024

5.9.1 ASHVIN KPI50 Marketing

One of the central goals of the ASHVIN project was to onboard 50 construction sites to the Digital Twin Platform (as part of WP7 Demonstrations). To achieve this, a variety of communication actions and strategies were used to engage with construction stakeholders and encourage them to participate in the initiative that we branded and called **#WINASHVIN**. These activities included creating branding materials such as a **marketing flyer**¹⁷ and a

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/7777391>

booklet¹⁸ showcasing the opportunity for external projects to onboard the ASHVIN Digital Twin platform. Also, we conducted webinars and calling to join through the podcast. Additionally, newsletters, emailing, website home page updates, blog articles and social media campaigns were employed to promote the opportunity. One of the most impactful engagement tactics was partners' one-to-one engagement with their respective contacts.

Figure 47 WinASHVIN Flyer

As a summary, the following ways contributed to promote the ASHVIN Open Call towards the target stakeholders:

- The banner and booklet were distributed during onsite events such as the **BuildingSmart conference in Poland** (May 2023) and the **BIMCon Summit in Romania** (October 2023). The booklet was also uploaded to the open repository, shared by partner networks, and promoted with a social media campaign during the **"World Creativity and Innovation Week"** on April 17th, 2023.
- Technical **webinar #1** and technical **webinar #2** were organised to call interested stakeholders to join the Digital Twin Platform.
- Each episode of the **"Innovation Stories"** podcast series also encouraged participation. **All the audiovisual campaign had 513 views.**
- ASHVIN started the promotion of the opportunity through **newsletters in the 5th issue** released in March 2023. The LinkedIn newsletter was also launched, and the **5th issue** was replicated along with the **Open Call opportunity** for EU construction projects. The **Joint Flash** and the **7th issue** contained information about the initiative, showcasing the number of onboarded construction projects.
- **From February to December 2023**, ASHVIN promoted the call for construction projects on social media channels.
- ASHVIN **website homepage** was updated with the Open Call, and two blog articles were dedicated exclusively to the opportunity. Moreover, seven blog articles were

¹⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/7763246>

also published mentioning the call for applicants, including **webinar 1**, **webinar 2**, **BuildingSmart** conference, **BIMCon Summit**, the **13 construction sites onboarded** article, the **new demo sites onboarded** article and the **three-year taking stock** article.

Figure 48 WinASHVIN OpenCall featured on the project website

Finally, to ensure a coordinated voice and message, ASHVIN created and shared a **communication toolkit** for communication channels (social media, newsletter, and articles). This helped 4 external public and private stakeholders who were interested in spreading the word about the opportunity: GENCAT, BUILD-UP, ECTP Organisation and HADEA.

Figure 49 HaDEA reweet of the WinASHVIN Open Call Post

Figure 50 ECTP Communication on WINASHVIN Open Call

5.9.2 European Thematic Campaigns

The second element of the communication campaigns that were carried out throughout the second half of the project is the European thematic campaigns that focused on showcasing the relevant European policies and international thematic day and share how these are implemented within the ASHVIN project. The presented topics included the following:

- The **European Year of Skills’ campaign** raised awareness about the importance of providing training and upskilling opportunities to construction workers for green and digital transitions. The blog article (published in January 2023) titled "[Beyond the ASHVIN Tools: Training and Upskilling](#)" highlights the lack of digital skills in the construction industry and how our academic partners are working towards improving knowledge circulation, attracting young people, and reducing the digital gap.
- **The International Day of Women and Girls in Science** takes place every February. To mark this celebration, we published a dedicated blog article (February 2023) entitled "[ASHVIN Observes the International Day of Women and Girls in Science](#)".
- In March 2023, the focus was **on innovation and digital decade** as we published an article entitled "[Innovation and Creativity: Problem-Solving through Digital Solutions in the Construction Sector](#)".
- The United Nations **World Day for Safety and Health at Work** takes place annually in May, and to explain how the ASHVIN solution can improve safety at the construction sites, we proposed a dedicated article (May 2023) "[ASHVIN’s Approach to Safety in the Construction Industry](#)".
- On the **World Environment Day**, the 5th of June, 2023, we published an article about improving efficiency in using resourcing with the support of digital tools "[World](#)

Environment Day: ASHVIN’s Contribution to a Resource-Efficient European Construction Industry”/

- Regarding the Europe Day, ASHVIN has published a dedicated post on social networks to underline the importance of a construction industry that has an enduring positive impact on our European society.

**International Day of
Women and Girls in Science**

Christina Claenson Johnson

Figure 51 Women in Science Day Banner

5.9.3 ASHVIN tools for all construction phases

The ASHVIN digital twin system supports the three different phases of the construction projects, **design, construction, and maintenance**. This campaign, structured equally in three parts, focused on sharing the main developed tools for each of the phases and how these tools were piloted across the ASHVIN demonstration sites. Also, we grouped all public deliverables and scientific articles that treated each of these specific phases. This series of articles include:

- The article [Revolutionising Infrastructure Maintenance: The ASHVIN Project’s Digital Twin Technology](#) (published in September 2023) presents briefly the three ASHVIN tools (GISI, RISA and MatchFem) how they support civil engineered assets maintenance and how these have been applied in real-life scenarios.
- The blog post [Pioneering Digital Twin Technologies for Construction and Building Projects – Discover ASHVIN’s Innovation](#) (published in October 2023) explains the develop digital twin tools for the construction phase (DES, 4DV-C, SMT and CMT), and how these have been implemented across three different demonstration sites.
- The article [ASHVIN Digital Twin Solution Enables Enhanced Design and Planning](#) (published in December 2023) showcases the three ASHVIN tools (EDB, BRICs and GEN) supporting the decision making and risk assessment in the design project phase and the two related pilot sites.

Revolutionising Infrastructure Maintenance: The ASHVIN Project's Digital Twin Technology

Figure 52 Banner of the article about ASHVIN for maintenance

5.9.4 Demonstration Sites

The project has involved in total 10 demonstration sites that contribute to developing and testing the ASHVIN digital twin technology. These sites are either building design and construction projects or infrastructure assets (e.g., bridges, airport runway, motorways) that need to be maintained operational over time. The communication campaign about the research progress of the demonstration sites took place during the last 18 project months. The strategy was to draft a dedicated article and related social media posts for each of the demonstration sites. These articles presented the demonstration site (location, project type, involved external stakeholders), how the ASHVIN system was deployed at the site and which tools were used for data collection to create a digital twin. Also, in shared insights about the faced challenges in running the ASHVIN solution on site and first results of the experiment.

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #1 SUCCESSFULLY FINALIZED

October 10, 2022

ASHVIN project is developing a digital solution will combine an open-source digital twin platform and integrated applications helping to reinforce productivity and safety of construction sites and maintenance operations. The implementation of...

[READ MORE](#)

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #5 "KINEUM OFFICE BUILDING" IN SWEDEN IS RUNNING

November 14, 2022

The ASHVIN solution using digital twin technologies will boost the European construction industry making it more performant, more sustainable, and safer. This system, combining a set of digital twin applications connected to...

[READ MORE](#)

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #10 "QUAY WALL IN THE NETHERLANDS" SUPPORTING THE OPERATIONS AND FUTURE CONSTRUCTION WORKS

December 1, 2023

The ASHVIN solution uses digital twin technologies to boost construction site management, making it more efficient while reducing costs, increasing productivity and safety while anticipating risks. ASHVIN offers an IoT-driven digital...

[READ MORE](#)

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #3 "AIRPORT RUNWAY IN CROATIA" SUCCESSFULLY CONDUCTED

March 16, 2023

We have finalised the data collection, condition assessment and maintenance planning model with the GISi and RISA tools! The ASHVIN solution uses digital twin technologies to boost construction site management, making it...

[READ MORE](#)

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #6 "OFFICE BUILDINGS IN SPAIN" FINALISED DATA COLLECTION

July 26, 2023

The ASHVIN solution uses digital twin technologies to boost construction site management, making it more efficient while reducing costs, more productive while using all gathered data and safer while anticipating risks. ASHVIN...

[READ MORE](#)

ASHVIN DEMO SITE #9 "SPORTS STADIUM ROOF STRUCTURE" – SUPPORT TO ASSET MAINTENANCE WITH DIGITAL TWINS

May 18, 2023

The ASHVIN project develops a set of digital twinning alternatives targeting the European construction sector and civil infrastructures. These alternatives allow connecting IoT-enabled digital twin platforms to different digital twin tools with...

[READ MORE](#)

Figure 53 Examples of the ASHVIN Demo Site Articles

The following table lists all the demonstration site articles and their publication dates. These were published regularly from October 2022 until December 2023, and each article included a social media posting campaign lasting for one month.

Table 20 Summary of the ASHVIN Demo Site Articles

#	Demo Site Name	Link to the article	Publication date
1.	Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain	www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/10/ashvin-demo-site-1-successfully-finalized/	10/10/2022
2.	Building Renovation	www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/19/ashvin-demo-site-2-building-renovation-in-poland-and-better-planning-of-renovation-process/	19/06/2023
3.	Airport runway in Croatia	www.ashvin.eu/2023/03/16/ashvin-demo-site-3-airport-runway-in-croatia-successfully-conducted/	16/03/2023
4.	Logistics hall construction in Germany	<i>Lacking the external stakeholders did not agree to publish any information.</i>	
5.	Kineum office building in Sweden	www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/14/ashvin-demo-site-5-kineum-office-building-in-sweden-is-running/	14/11/2022
6.	Office Buildings	www.ashvin.eu/2023/07/26/ashvin-demo-site-6-office-buildings-in-spain-finalised-data-collection/	26/07/2023

7.	Bridges in highway network in Spain	<i>Pending in January 2023 – to be finalised by UPC</i>	
8.	Footbridge in Germany	<i>Pending in January 2023 – the approval for its publication to be confirmed by the external stakeholder</i>	
9.	Sport stadium roof structure	www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/18/ashvin-demo-site-9-sports-stadium-roof-structure-support-to-asset-maintenance-with-digital-twins/	18/05/2023
10	Quay wall in the Netherlands	www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/01/ashvin-demo-site-10-quay-wall-in-the-netherlands-supporting-the-operations-and-future-construction-works/	01/12/2023

Moreover, the dissemination of the project results used the research results of the demonstration sites, especially in **9 scientific publications in conferences and journals** were issued based on the demonstration site research.

Table 21 Scientific publications related to the ASHVIN Demo Sites

Related demo sites	Title	Publication spot	Link
DS #1	Towards Automated Pipelines for Processing Load Test Data On A High-Speed Railway Bridge In Spain Using A Digital Twin	39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC 2022)	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/07/15/isarc-2022-international-symposium-on-automation-and-robotics-in-construction/
DS #6	Closing the gap between concrete maturity monitoring and nonlinear time-dependent fem analysis through a digital twin. Case study: post-tensioned concrete slab of an office building, Barcelona, Spain	39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC 2022)	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/07/15/isarc-2022-international-symposium-on-automation-and-robotics-in-construction/
DS #9	Automated pipeline for the analysis of a scale-reduced steel cable net	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures 2022	https://zenodo.org/record/8314890
DS #1	Ground-Based interferometer radars for load tests of long-span arch bridges. Case study: Almonte and El Tajo Viaducts, Extremadura, Spain	International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management 2022	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/07/15/international-conference-on-bridge-maintenance-safety-and-management-2022/
DS #1	Digital twinning during load tests of railway bridges - case study: the high-speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain	Structure and Infrastructure Engineering Journal (July 2023)	https://zenodo.org/records/10159425
DS #3	Measurements, Simulation, Analysis and Geolocation in a Digital Twin tool for bridge management	Eurostruct Conference 2023	https://zenodo.org/records/10057697
DS #3	Inspection and maintenance KPIs to support decision-making integrated into Digital Twin	Eurostruct Conference 2023	https://zenodo.org/records/10057697

	tool		7756
Several sites	Knowledge graph-based data integration system for digital twins of built assets	Automation in Construction, 156(2023)(05/09), ISSN: 1872-7891, 2023.	https://zenodo.org/records/10058228
DS #6	Fusion of Environmental Sensors for Occupancy Detection in a Real Construction Site	MDPI Sensors Journal, Special Issue: Sensor Data Fusion Analysis for Broad Applications: 2nd Edition, ISSN: 1424-8220, 2023.	https://zenodo.org/records/10058228

In addition, partners created **six videos about the demonstration sites**. The aim of these videos was to provide insights to the research performed on the sites.

Table 22 Produced videos about the ASHVIN demo sites

Related demo site	Video title	Link
#1	#ASHVIN Demo Site 1 - #Bridges for high-speed railways in Spain with #digitaltwin	https://youtu.be/8BTwk6iKuzc?si=lk97JGL1CLIdPx2f
#2	Demo #2: 3D Scanning for a Digital Twin	https://youtu.be/YNbyGvill0U?si=PgT99iFM7RlaMGin
#5	Demosite #5: Kineum office building in Sweden	https://youtu.be/f_KsGQNEegQ?si=D9aB6Ra291Zg6jst
#5	ASHVIN Demo Site 5 #Kineum office building in Sweden	https://youtu.be/xWejAzDyCmk?si=C_vxktEWsPYrEPVu
#6	Demo #6: From LIDAR to Digital Twins	https://youtu.be/E_z8awBj024?si=WT2MN6XJoR-2fnOQ
#9	Demo #9: Scale reduced cable net - Tests on Sensors and MatchFEM	https://youtu.be/WHUH-RWOT94?si=xkGlb69HATwWmNnW

5.9.5 ASHVIN Impact Stories

ASHVIN organised a campaign to introduce members of the team who were working as Work Package leaders. The campaign aimed to present their viewpoints on the impact of the project and the feedback received from external stakeholders. There was a video for each team member, and a joint blog article that compiled all these videos together. In total, these videos were viewed 90 times, and to more videos are about to be released before the end of the project.

Table 23 ASHVIN Impact Stories

Date of publication	Title	Views
October 3rd, 2023	#ImpactStories :Encompassing data collected with sensors and devices by Rolando Chacon	32
November 16th, 2023	#ImpactStories: Managing the technical developments of ASHVIN by Rahul Tomar	31
January 22nd, 2024	#ImpactStories : Collecting and using data for efficient construction management by Manuel Jungmann	27

Figure 54 Banner of the ASHVIN Impact stories

5.9.6 ASHVIN Research Stories

ASHVIN conducted a campaign of interviews with 7 members of the research team working on the project. Each episode included two to three-minute video interviews and a blog article that provided further explanations about their work. These videos, listed in the following table, received in total **170+ views on YouTube**.

Table 24 ASHVIN Impact Stories

Date of publication	Title	Views	Website article
January 2nd, 2024	#ResearchStories: Human factors of ASHVIN by Selma Toktas Post-Doc Research Fellow	28	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Human factors of ASHVIN by Selma Toktas Post-Doc Research Fellow
January 10th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Maintenance of Buildings and Bridges by Carlos Ramonell, PhD Research Student	7	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Maintenance of Buildings and Bridges by Carlos Ramonell, PhD Research Student
January 16th, 2024	#ResearchStories : AI-driven methodologies by Marios Krestenitis, Research Assistant	9	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: AI-driven methodologies by Marios Krestenitis, Research Assistant
January 24th, 2024	#ResearchStories :Virtual representation of the multiphysics of an asset, Héctor Posada, PhD Student	72	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Virtual representations of the multiphysics of an asset by Héctor Posada, PhD Research Student
January 31st, 2024	#ResearchStories : Computer science abilities by Panagiotis Giannakeris, MsC Research Fellow	12	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Computer science abilities by Panagiotis Giannakeris, MsC Research Fellow
February 6th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Conceptual engineering	46	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning:

	designs with Joan Evelyn Ongodia, Research Assistant		Conceptual engineering designs with Joan Evelyn Ongodia, Research Assistant
February 13th, 2024	#ResearchStories : Integrating and fusing data by Athina Tsanousa, Postdoc Researcher	6	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Integrating and fusing data by Athina Tsanousa, Postdoc Researcher

Figure 55 Banner of the ASHVIN researcher campaign

6 CONCLUSIONS

The communication and dissemination activities contribute to the impact of our research project, making stakeholders aware of the project's results and enabling them to deploy the public results as a part of their work in researching, developing, or implementing digital twin technologies for the construction sector. At the start of the project, a set of key performance indicators were set, and an overall strategy was designed, which helped to monitor and assess the project's performance and progress in communication and dissemination. Now, at the end of the project, we can proudly state that all the fixed objectives were met, and we even exceeded these expectations thanks to the continuous engagement of the entire ASHVIN consortium.

Moreover, now that the project's results are delivered, the shared ambition of the ASHVIN team is to sustain these even beyond the project's ending. We will ensure that the most important communication channels will stay alive, and the major scientific outputs will continue to be available in open access, so that the target stakeholders can continue to be informed and to use these results.

The **ASHVIN website**¹⁹ will be available until two years after the project's ending (March 2026). Also, the team continues to update there the final deliverables and publications that are published at the very end of the project.

The established **ASHVIN Community on LinkedIn**²⁰ will continue to live, and the team will share their relevant updates to ensure that all final public results of the projects are shared with this community. This account will remain open without a set delay, and it is managed by AUSTRALO.

All publications listed on **ASHVIN's open repository on Zenodo library**²¹ shall remain accessible for interested stakeholders. This page will stay alive without a final deadline, as it is free of charge, and AUSTRALO oversees maintaining it.

In addition, **all created visual branding and communication elements** will guide the road for follow-up activities running under the related schemes by the European Commission. The ASHVIN project has been a great experiment to understand better what kind of communication style and content are attractive to the stakeholders, and these lessons will be taken to new digital innovation projects on the construction sector. For instance, the Webinar #2 focusing on supporting maintenance with digital twin technologies showed that there is a great interest in this specific topic which could be exploited even further.

Thanks to the continuous and varied communication and dissemination activities, the ASHVIN project will leave its footprint in the world of the research and innovation in digital twin technologies for the construction industry. And it will be followed by new projects and initiatives, such as **Reincarnate**²², **HumanTech**²³, **SEISMEC**²⁴ or **Tech4EU Cluster**²⁵, that continue informing and engaging stakeholders in the digital construction sector.

¹⁹ www.ashvin.eu

²⁰ www.linkedin.com/company/ashvin-h2020

²¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/ashvin2020/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

²² <https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

²³ <https://humantech-horizon.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/seismec/>

ANNEX 1 – PUBLICATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCES

The ASHVIN project presented **12 publications in international scientific conferences**, and these publications are in open access.

Table 25 List of publications in scientific conferences

Title	Authors	Title of the Conference	Publication date	Peer-reviewed?	DOI	Repository Link
Virtual construction with digital twins – The key for leanly planned complex construction systems	Timo Hartmann	Kongress Zukunft Bau Wien	2021	No	10.5281/zenodo.5977715	https://zenodo.org/record/5977715
Platology: A Digital Twin Ontology Suite for the Complete Lifecycle of Infrastructure	Khan, Rehan; Tomar, Rahul; Hartmann, Timo; Ungureanu, Lucian; Chacón Flores, Rolando Antonio; Ibrahim, Ahmed	29th Workshop on Intelligent Computing in Engineering (EG ICE 2022)	2022	Yes	10.5281/zenodo.8314844	https://zenodo.org/record/8314844
Closing the Gap Between Concrete Maturity Monitoring and Nonlinear Time-Dependent Fem Analysis Through a Digital Twin	Posada Cárcamo, Héctor José; Chacón Flores, Rolando Antonio; Ungureanu, Lucian; Garcia Carrera, David	39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC 2022)	2022	No	ISBN 978-952-69524-2-0.	https://zenodo.org/records/10793471

Towards Automated Pipelines for Processing Load Test Data On A High-Speed Railway Bridge In Spain Using A Digital Twin	Ramonell Cazador, Carlos; Chacón Flores, Rolando Antonio	39th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC 2022)	2022	No	ISBN 978-952-69524-2-0.	https://zenodo.org/records/10793518
Automated pipeline for the analysis of a scale-reduced steel cable net	Rolando Chacón, Burkhard Krenn, Càrol Puig-Polo	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures 2022	2022	Yes	10.1002/cepa.1851	https://zenodo.org/record/8314890
Low-light image enhancement based on U-Net and Haar”	Batziou, E., Ioannidis, K., Patras, I., Vrochidis, S., Kompatsiaris, I.	the 29th International Conference on Multimedia Modeling (MMM 2023)	2023	yes	10.5281/zenodo.7669741	https://zenodo.org/record/7669741
Seasonal analysis of a 846 long steel box girder bridge using Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS) and FE-models”	Carlos Ramonell; Rolando Chacón	Annual Stability Conference Structural Stability Research Council	12/04/2023	Yes	10.5281/zenodo.7906953	https://zenodo.org/record/7906953
A combined Digital Twin and Location-Based Management System	Manuel Jungmann, Timo Hartmann, Rahul Tomar, Lucian Ungureanu	IGLC conference	02/07/2023	Yes	10.24928/2023/0184	https://zenodo.org/record/8113458

<p>A real-time discrete event simulation tool for data-based construction management</p>	<p>Manuel Jungmann (TUB) Timo Hartmann (TUB)</p>	<p>EG ICE 2023</p>	<p>04/07/2023</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>10.5281/zenodo.8314790</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/record/8314790</p>
<p>Measurements, Simulation, Analysis and Geolocation in a Digital Twin tool for bridge management</p>	<p>Rolando Chacón, Carlos Ramonell Cazador, Héctor Posada Cárcamo, Rahul Tomar, Christian Martínez de la Rosa, and Irina Stipanović.</p>	<p>Eurostruct Conference</p>	<p>27/09/2023</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>10.1002/cepa.2017</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10057697</p>
<p>Inspection and maintenance KPIs to support decision-making integrated into Digital Twin tool</p>	<p>Irina Stipanović, Sandra Škarić Palić, Joan Ramon Casas, Rolando Chacón, and Emir Ganić</p>	<p>Eurostruct Conference</p>	<p>27/09/2023</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>10.1002/cepa.2137</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10057756</p>
<p>A framework for 3D modelling of construction sites using aerial imagery and semantic NeRFs</p>	<p>Panagiotis Vrachnos, Marios Krestenitis, Ilias Koulalis, Konstantinos Ioannidis and Stefanos Vrochidis</p>	<p>30th International Conference on Multimedia Modelling</p>	<p>January 2024</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53302-0_13</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10777564</p>

ANNEX 2 - LIST PUBLICATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS

The project research was published in **7 scientific articles** published in peer-reviewed journals, and all these peer-reviewed papers are openly accessible.

Table 26 List of scientific publications in journals

Title	Authors	Title of the Journal	Publication	DOI	Repository Link
Open-source terrestrial laser scanner for the virtualization of geometrical entities in AEC classrooms	Carlos Ramonell; Rolando Chacón	Computer Applications in Engineering Education	Volume30, Issue4	10.1002/cae.22499	https://zenodo.org/record/6034683
Detecting anomalies and denoising monitoring data from sensors: A smart data approach	Weili Fanga, Yixiao Shaob, Peter E.D. Lovec, Timo Hartmann, Wenli Liu	Advanced Engineering Informatics	Volume 55, January 2023, 101870	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2022.101870	https://zenodo.org/records/10792775
Requirements and challenges for infusion of SHM systems within Digital Twins platforms	Rolando Chacón, Irina Stipanovic	Structure and Infrastructure Engineering	28/06/2023	10.1080/15732479.2023.2225486	https://zenodo.org/record/8108683

<p>Digital twinning during load tests of railway bridges -Case Study: The high speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain.</p>	<p>Rolando Chacón*, Hector Posada, Carlos Ramonell, Pablo Sierra, Rahul Tomar, Christian Martinez de la Rosa, Alejandro Rodriguez, Ilias Koulalis, Konstantinos Ioannidis Stefan Wagmeister</p>	<p>Structure and Infrastructure Engineering Journal</p>	<p>09/10/2023</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1080/15732479.2023.2264840</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10159425</p>
<p>A Knowledge Graph-based data integration system for digital twins of built assets</p>	<p>Carlos Ramonell, Rolando Chacón, Hector Posada</p>	<p>Automation in Construction</p>	<p>05/10/2023</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.105109</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10058228</p>
<p>Fusion of environmental sensors for occupancy detection in a real construction site</p>	<p>Athina Tsanousa, Chrysoula Moschou, Evangelos Bektsis, Stefanos Vrochidis, Ioannis Kompatsiaris</p>	<p>MDPI Sensors Journal : Special Issue: Sensor Data Fusion Analysis for Broad Applications: 2nd Edition</p>	<p>04/12/2023</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.3390/s23239596</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10418897</p>
<p>Digital twinning of building construction processes. Case study: a reinforced concrete cast-in structure.</p>	<p>Chacón R., Posada H., Ramonell C, Jungmann M., Hartmann T., Khan R., Tomar R. (2024)</p>	<p>the Journal of Building Engineering</p>	<p>11 January 2024</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobe.2024.108522</p>	<p>https://zenodo.org/records/10569603</p>

ANNEX 3 - LIST OF RELATED SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS WITH A RESTRICTED ACCESS

The project research was published in **6 scientific publications in conference proceedings** but their access is restricted, and hence not count in the KPIs.

Publication type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal/Proc./Book	Publication date	Is Peer-reviewed?	DOI	Repository Link
Publication in Conference proceedings	Geometrical digital twinning of a tapered, horizontally curved composite box girder bridge	Rolando Chacón, Carlos Ramonell, Càrol Puig-Polo, Enrique Mirambell	International Colloquium on Stability and Ductility of Steel Structures 2022	Volume5, Issue4	Yes	10.1002/cepa.1727	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/cepa.1727
Publication in Conference proceedings	Ground-Based interferometer radars for load tests of long-span arch bridges. Case study: Almonte and El Tajo Viaducts, Extremadura, Spain	Alejandro Rodríguez, J. Fuente, R. Fabregad, R. Chacón, C. Ramonell	International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management	2022	Yes	10.1201/9781003322641-271	https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.1201/9781003322641-271/ground-based-interferometer-radars-load-tests-long-span-arch-bridges-case-study-almonte-el-tajo-viaducts-extremadura-spain-rodr%C3%ADguez-fabregad-%C3%A1lvarez-chac%C3%B3n-ramonell

Publication in Conference proceedings	On the digital twinning of routine load tests in railway bridges. Case study: high speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain	Chacon, R.; Posada, H.; Ramonell, C.; Sierra, P.; Rodriguez Gonzalez, A.; Koulalis, I.; Ioannidis, K.; Vrochidis, S.; Tomar, R.; Freitag, S.; Wagmeister, S.; Teodorovic, M.	International Conference on Bridge Maintenance, Safety and Management	2022	Yes	10.1201/9781003322641-98	https://www.routledge.com/Bridge-Safety-Maintenance-Management-Life-Cycle-Resilience-and-Sustainability/Casas-Frangopol-Turmo/p/book/9781003322641
Publication in Conference proceedings	A survey for image based methods in construction: from images to digital twins	Koulalis, I., Dourvas, N., Triantafyllidis, T., Ioannidis, K., Vrochidis, S., & Kompatsiaris	In 19th International Conference on Content-based Multimedia Indexing (CBMI 2022), Graz, Austria, 14-16 September 2022,	2022	Yes	https://doi.org/10.1145/3549555.3549594	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3549555.3549594
Publication in Conference proceedings	Real-time duration extraction of crane works for data-driven discrete event simulation	Manuel Jungmann, Lucian unguoreanu , Timo Hartmann , Rolando Chacon and Hector Posada	Winter Simulation Conference 2022, 14-16 December 2022, Singapore	2022	Yes	10.1109/WSC57314.2022.10015250	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10015250

<p>Publication in Conference proceedings</p>	<p>I-Twin. Computational twin connectors for I-profiles. Towards unforeseen interoperability of digital tools</p>	<p>Hector Posada, Rolando Chacón, Carlos Ramonell (UPC).</p>	<p>Eurosteel Conference 2023</p>	<p>12/09/2023</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>https://doi.org/10.1002/cepa.2661</p>	<p>https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/cepa.2661</p>
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ANNEX 4 – LIST OF THE OPENLY ACCESSIBLE PROJECT RESULTS ON ZENODO

Over 60+ ASHVIN related public documents have been released on the open repository, Zenodo. This annex lists them providing their type, title, and direct link to the documents.

Table 27 Table 3 ASHVIN Zenodo Library Items

Type	Title	Link
Scientific publication	Towards Automated Pipelines for Processing Load Test Data on an HS Railway Bridge in Spain using a Digital Twin	https://zenodo.org/records/10793518
Scientific publication	Closing the Gap Between Concrete Maturity Monitoring and Nonlinear Time-dependent FEM Analysis	https://zenodo.org/records/10793471
Scientific publication	Detecting anomalies and de-noising monitoring data from sensors: A smart data approach	https://zenodo.org/records/10792775
Scientific publication	A Framework for 3D Modelling of Construction Sites Using Aerial Imagery and Semantic NeRFs	https://zenodo.org/records/10777564
Scientific publication	Digital twinning of building construction processes. Case study: A reinforced concrete cast-in structure	https://zenodo.org/records/10569603
Scientific publication	Fusion of Environmental Sensors for Occupancy Detection in a Real Construction Site	https://zenodo.org/records/10418897
Deliverable	Deliverable 6.6 Availability Of Measured Maintenance Data Of Infrastructure For Public Domain	https://zenodo.org/records/10351476
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter 7 - Marking the end of the 3rd project year	https://zenodo.org/records/10228596
Scientific publication	Digital twinning during load tests of railway bridges - case study: the high-speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain	https://zenodo.org/records/10159425
Scientific publication	Knowledge graph-based data integration system for digital twins of built assets	https://zenodo.org/records/10058228
Scientific publication	Inspection and maintenance KPIs to support decision making integrated into Digital Twin tool	https://zenodo.org/records/10057756
Research Data	Environmental sensor data for occupancy detection	https://zenodo.org/records/8203278
Scientific publication	Measurements, Simulation, Analysis and Geolocation in a Digital Twin tool for bridge management	https://zenodo.org/records/10057697
Scientific publication	Automated pipeline for the analysis of a scale-reduced steel cable net	https://zenodo.org/record/8314890
Scientific publication	Platology: A Digital Twin Ontology Suite for the Complete Lifecycle of Infrastructure	https://zenodo.org/record/8314844
Deliverable	D4.6 Visualizing and dashboarding construction	https://zenodo.org/record/8314556

	activities based on digital twin data	
Newsletter	Digital Building Twin Cluster - Joint Newsletter #1	https://zenodo.org/record/8297852
Scientific publication	Combined Digital Twin and Location-Based Management System	https://zenodo.org/record/8113458
Scientific publication	Requirements and challenges for infusion of SHM systems within Digital Twin platforms	https://zenodo.org/record/8108683
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter #6	https://zenodo.org/record/8094642
Deliverable	Deliverable 4.4 Risk Management	https://zenodo.org/record/8074932
Scientific publication	Ontologies in digital twin: Methodology, lessons learned and practical approach	https://zenodo.org/record/8074139
Communication item	ASHVIN Technical Webinar 2 Agenda : Maintenance of Civil Engineering Assets	https://zenodo.org/record/7962457
Deliverable	Deliverable 5.3 A set of KPIs to plan a safe risk-based maintenance	https://zenodo.org/record/7928412
Deliverable	Deliverable 5.2 " Digital-Twin Enabled multi-physics simulation and model matching"	https://zenodo.org/record/7928384
Scientific publication	Seasonal analysis of an 846 long steel box girder bridge using Terrestrial Laser Scanners (TLS) and FE-models	https://zenodo.org/record/7906953
Deliverable	D3.2 Digital Twin-based Geo-Monitoring	https://zenodo.org/record/7794442
Deliverable	D2.3: Parametric design to optimize productivity, resource efficiency, and safety	https://zenodo.org/record/7794389
Communication item	ASHVIN Marketing One-Pager	https://zenodo.org/record/7777391
Communication item	ASHVIN Marketing Brochure	https://zenodo.org/record/7763246
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter#5	https://zenodo.org/record/7705189
Communication item	ASHVIN Technical Webinar - Presentation of the Digital Twin Platform	https://zenodo.org/record/7684693
Scientific publication	Low-light image enhancement based on U-Net and Haar wavelet	https://zenodo.org/record/7669741
Newsletter	ASHVIN's 4th Newsletter	https://zenodo.org/record/7372936
Deliverable	D4.3 Digital Twin supported lean project planning, control and risk management	https://zenodo.org/record/7313175
Deliverable	D2.2 Evaluation and recommendations for evidence-based design for productivity, resource efficiency, and safety based on historical digital twin data	https://zenodo.org/record/7234679
Scientific publication	Open-source terrestrial laser scanner for the virtualization of geometrical entities in AEC classrooms	https://zenodo.org/record/6034683
Deliverable	D4.5 Virtual Commissioning Model	https://zenodo.org/record/7220249

Deliverable	D3.3 Data Fusion Methods and Digital Twin-based IoT Data Processing Pipelines	https://zenodo.org/record/7220164
Deliverable	D4.2 Discrete Event Simulation Formalism for Productive, Resource Efficient, and Safe Construction Planning	https://zenodo.org/record/7220125
Deliverable	D3.1 Visual Analysis for Real Sensing	https://zenodo.org/record/7220100
Deliverable	D1.4 Digital Twin Interoperability in the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220073
Deliverable	D1.5 Safety and Privacy for Digital Twins in the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220040
Deliverable	D1.2 An Ontology for Digital Twin Models for the Construction Industry	https://zenodo.org/record/7220000
Software	ASHVIN Construction Digital Twin API	https://zenodo.org/record/7127785
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter Volume 3	https://zenodo.org/record/6523493
Deliverable	D8.3 IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND EXPLOITATION INTERIM REPORT	https://zenodo.org/record/6405241
Deliverable	D8.2 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION INTERIM REPORT	https://zenodo.org/record/6405239
Deliverable	D5.1 SHM DIGITAL TWIN REQUIREMENTS FOR RESIDENTIAL, INDUSTRIAL BUILDINGS AND BRIDGES	https://zenodo.org/record/6405220
Scientific publication	Virtual construction with digital twins – The key for leanly planned complex construction systems	https://zenodo.org/record/5977715
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter Volume 2	https://zenodo.org/record/5761147
Deliverable	D7.1 ASHVIN TECHNOLOGY DEMONSTRATION PLAN	https://zenodo.org/record/5542985
Deliverable	D4.1 A SET OF KPIS TO PLAN AND MONITOR PRODUCTIVE, RESOURCE EFFICIENT, AND SAFE CONSTRUCTION SITES	https://zenodo.org/record/5542981
Deliverable	D2.1 A SET OF KPIS TO DESIGN FOR PRODUCTIVITY, RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, AND SAFETY	https://zenodo.org/record/5542975
Newsletter	ASHVIN Newsletter Volume 1	https://zenodo.org/record/5026176
Communication item	LC-008-EEB projects Joint Press Release	https://zenodo.org/record/4915813
Communication item	BIMprove Brochure (A4)	https://zenodo.org/record/4557184
Deliverable	D4.1 BIMprove Impact Master Plan	https://zenodo.org/record/4299022
Deliverable	D1.1 Launch Version of ASHVIN Platform	https://zenodo.org/record/4556836
Communication item	Press Release: ASHVIN & StandICT.eu 2023 MoU Signed	https://zenodo.org/record/4630657
Communication item	ASHVIN H2020 Roll Up Banner	https://zenodo.org/record/4671745
Communication	ASHVIN H2020 Poster	https://zenodo.org/record/4674292

item		
Communication item	ASHVIN One Pager - Brochure (A4)	https://zenodo.org/record/4674295
Deliverable	D6.1 STANDARDIZATION PLAN	https://zenodo.org/record/4707097

ANNEX 5 – LIST OF THE PRODUCED BLOG ARTICLES ABOUT THE ASHVIN SYSTEM AND THE PROJECT RESULTS

The following table listed 102 articles that were published on the knowledge hub – page of the project’s website since the mid-term reporting (from May 2022 onwards).

Table 28 List of ASHVIN blog articles

Date	Title	Hyperlink
22/03/2024	The Mainflux IoT Platform: One of the Cornerstones in the ASHVIN Digital Twin System	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/22/the-mainflux-iot-platform-one-of-the-cornerstones-in-the-ashvin-digital-twin-system/
12/03/2024	ASHVIN represented at the ECTP Conference 2024 - Two Decades Shaping Smart and Green Building	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/12/ashvin-represented-at-the-ectp-conference-2024-two-decades-shaping-smart-and-green-building/
11/03/2024	ASHVIN powers the SEISMEC project symposium in Rotterdam	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/11/ashvin-powers-the-seismec-project-symposium-in-rotterdam/
07/03/2024	Beyond the Final Page: Reflecting on Recommendations and Feedback by ASHVIN’s Advisory Board Members	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/07/beyond-the-final-page-reflecting-on-recommendations-and-feedback-by-ashvins-advisory-board-members/
07/03/2024	Scientific Publication: Towards Automated Pipelines for Processing Load Test Data on an HS Railway Bridge in Spain using a Digital Twin	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/07/scientific-publication-towards-automated-pipelines-for-processing-load-test-data-on-an-hs-railway-bridge-in-spain-using-a-digital-twin/
07/03/2024	Scientific Publication: Closing the Gap Between Concrete Maturity Monitoring and Nonlinear Time-dependent FEM Analysis	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/03/07/scientific-publication-closing-the-gap-between-concrete-maturity-monitoring-and-nonlinear-time-dependent-fem-analysis/
22/02/2024	ASHVIN Interactive Webinar #3: Advancing Open Data for Future Infrastructure Maintenance	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/23/ashvin-interactive-webinar-3-advancing-open-data-for-future-infrastructure-maintenance/
22/02/2024	ASHVIN’s Sister Project Offers a Webinar Series about Digital Twin Technologies	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/22/ashvins-sister-project-offers-a-webinar-series-about-digital-twin-technologies/
13/02/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Integrating and fusing data by Athina Tsanousa, Postdoc Researcher	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/13/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-integrating-and-fusing-data-by-athina-tsanousa-postdoc-researcher/
06/02/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Conceptual engineering designs with Joan Evelyn Ongodia, Research Assistant	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/06/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-conceptual-engineering-designs-with-joan-evelyn-ongodia-research-assistant/
01/02/2024	ASHVIN at Transport Research Board Annual Meeting 2024 in Washington D.C, U.S	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/01/ashvin-at-transport-research-board-annual-meeting-2024-in-washington-d-c-u-s/
01/02/2024	INFRAPLAN Represented ASHVIN at the OLGA Project Conference Shaping Green Airport and Smart Cities	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/01/infraplan-represented-ashvin-at-the-olga-project-conference-shaping-green-airport-and-smart-cities/
30/01/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Computer science abilities by Panagiotis Giannakeris, MSc Research Fellow	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/30/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-computer-science-abilities-by-panagiotis-giannakeris-msc-research-fellow/
25/01/2024	New Scientific Publication in a Journal: Digital twinning of building construction processes. Case study: A reinforced concrete cast-in structure	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/02/20/new-scientific-publication-in-a-journal-digital-twinning-of-building-construction-processes-case-study-a-reinforced-concrete-cast-in-structure/
19/01/2024	ASHVIN’s 7th and Final General Assembly in Belgrade, Serbia	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/19/ashvins-7th-and-final-general-assembly-in-belgrade-serbia/
16/01/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: AI-driven methodologies by Marios Krestenitis, Research Assistant	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/16/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-ai-driven-methodologies-by-marios-krestenitis-research-assistant/
10/01/2024	ASHVIN’s Digital Twins: Transforming Infrastructure Data for Stakeholder Value	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/10/ashvins-digital-twins-transforming-infrastructure-data-for-stakeholder-value/
10/01/2024	Contribution of ASHVIN to the Structural Engineering Community – #OceaniaMeetsASHVIN	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/10/contribution-of-ashvin-to-the-structural-engineering-community-oceaniameetsashvin/
	Contribution of ASHVIN for educational activities – #OceaniaMeetsASHVIN	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/09/contribution-of-ashvin-for-educational-activities-oceaniameetsashvin/
09/01/2024	Contribution of ASHVIN to cross-pollinate research	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/09/contribution-of-ashvin-to-cross-pollinate-research-activities-with-international-centers-

	activities with international centers – #OceaniaMeetsASHVIN	oceanameetsashvin/
23/01/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Virtual representations of the multiphysics of an asset by Héctor Posada, PhD Research Student	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/23/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-virtual-representations-of-the-multiphysics-of-an-asset-by-hector-posada-phd-research-student/
09/01/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Maintenance of Buildings and Bridges by Carlos Ramonell, PhD Research Student	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/09/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-maintenance-of-buildings-and-bridges-by-carlos-ramonell-phd-research-student/
02/01/2024	Groundbreakers in Digital Twinning: Human factors of ASHVIN by Selma Toktas Post-Doc Research Fellow	https://www.ashvin.eu/2024/01/02/groundbreakers-in-digital-twinning-human-factors-of-ashvin-by-selma-toktas-post-doc-research-fellow/
21/12/2023	New scientific publication: Fusion of Environmental Sensors for Occupancy Detection in a Real Construction Site	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/21/new-scientific-publication-in-a-journal-fusion-of-environmental-sensors-for-occupancy-detection-in-a-real-construction-site/
11/12/2023	Deliverable 6.6 Availability Of Measured Maintenance Data Of Infrastructure For Public Domain	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/11/deliverable-6-6-availability-of-measured-maintenance-data-of-infrastructure-for-public-domain/
06/12/2023	ASHVIN Digital Twin Solution Enables Enhanced Design and Planning	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/06/ashvin-digital-twin-solution-enables-enhanced-design-and-planning
04/12/2023	13 New Construction Sites Onboarded to The ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/04/13-new-construction-sites-onboarded-to-the-ashvin-digital-twin-platform/
01/12/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #10 “Quay wall in the Netherlands” Supporting the Operations and Future Construction Works	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/12/01/ashvin-demo-site-10-quay-wall-in-the-netherlands-supporting-the-operations-and-future-construction-works/
27/11/2023	New Scientific Publication in a Journal: Digital twinning during load tests of railway bridges – case study: the high-speed railway network, Extremadura, Spain	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/27/new-scientific-publication-in-a-journal-digital-twinning-during-load-tests-of-railway-bridges-case-study-the-high-speed-railway-network-extremadura-spain/
20/11/2023	New scientific publication at EUROSTRUCT 2023: Inspection and maintenance KPIs to support decision making integrated into Digital Twin tool	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/20/ashvins-scientific-paper-on-inspection-and-maintenance-kpis-in-digital-twins-presented-at-the-eurostruct-conference-is-now-available/
16/11/2023	New scientific publication on a journal: A Knowledge Graph-based data integration system for digital twins of built assets	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/16/ashvin-has-a-new-scientific-paper-on-a-data-integration-system-for-digital-twins-of-built-assets/
09/11/2023	ASHVIN presents a scientific paper on a digital-twin-based tool for bridge management at the EUROSTRUCT conference	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/09/ashvin-presents-a-scientific-paper-on-a-digital-twin-based-tool-for-bridge-management-at-the-eurostruct-conference/
09/11/2023	ASHVIN participates in the 5th edition of the BIMcon Summit in Romania	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/09/ashvin-participates-in-the-5th-edition-of-the-bimcon-summit-in-romania/
09/11/2023	Taking stock of the ASHVIN project: 3-years of Research and Innovation for Digital Building Twin	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/09/taking-stock-of-the-ashvin-project-3-years-of-research-and-innovation-for-digital-building-twin/
09/10/2023	Pioneering Digital Twin Technologies for Construction and Building Projects – Discover ASHVIN’s Innovation	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/10/09/pioneering-digital-twin-technologies-for-construction-and-building-projects-discover-ashvins-innovation/
04/10/2023	ASHVIN Impact Stories: Experts sharing views on the Future Digital Building Twin	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/11/16/ashvin-impact-stories-experts-sharing-views-on-the-future-digital-building-twin/
02/10/2023	Two Scientific Publications Presented at Eurostruct Conference 2023	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/10/03/scientific-publication-presented-at-eurostruct-conference-2023/
15/09/2023	ASHVIN Presented A New Scientific Publication At Eurosteel 2023 Conference	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/09/15/ashvin-presented-a-new-scientific-publication-at-eurosteel-2023-conference/
14/09/2023	ASHVIN’s latest contribution to the European standardisation of Digital Twin technologies	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/09/14/ashvins-latest-contribution-to-the-european-standardisation-of-digital-twin-technologies/
11/09/2023	Revolutionising Infrastructure Maintenance: The ASHVIN Project’s Digital Twin Technology	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/09/11/revolutionising-infrastructure-maintenance-the-ashvin-projects-digital-twin-technology/
27/07/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #6 “Office Buildings in Spain” Finalised Data Collection	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/07/26/ashvin-demo-site-6-office-buildings-in-spain-finalised-data-collection/

06/07/2023	ASHVIN Podcast - Innovation Stories	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/07/06/ashvin-mini-podcast-series-innovation-stories/
04/06/2023	New Scientific Publication: a Combined Digital Twin and Location-Based Management System	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/07/04/new-scientific-publication-a-combined-digital-twin-and-location-based-management-system/
29/06 /2023	ASHVIN Ontologies Presented in an Open Letter at the Open Research Europe	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/28/ashvin-ontologies-in-digital-twins-presented-in-an-open-letter-at-the-open-research-europe/
28/06/2023	New Scientific Publication: Requirements And Challenges for Infusion of SHM Systems Within Digital Twin Platforms	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/28/new-scientific-publication-requirements-and-challenges-for-infusion-of-shm-systems-within-digital-twin-platforms/
20/06/2023	The 6th Project Meeting in Stockholm, June 2023	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/20/the-6th-project-meeting-in-stockholm-june-2023/
19/06/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #2 “Building Renovation in Poland” and Better Planning of Renovation Process	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/19/ashvin-demo-site-2-building-renovation-in-poland-and-better-planning-of-renovation-process/
05/06/2023	World Environment Day: ASHVIN’s Contribution to a Resource-Efficient European Construction Industry	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/05/world-environment-day-ashvins-contribution-to-a-resource-efficient-european-construction-industry/
01/06/2023	ASHVIN Tools Showcased on the EU Innovation Radar	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/06/01/ashvin-tools-featured-on-the-eu-innovation-radar/
30/05/2023	ASHVIN Featured in Diari ARA. Media Outlet	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/30/ashvin-featured-in-diari-ara-media-outlet/
30/05/2023	ASHVIN Digital Toolkit Staged at the Computational Civil Engineering International Conference	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/30/ashvin-digital-toolkit-staged-at-the-computational-civil-engineering-international-conference/
30/05/2023	The ASHVIN Project Was Featured in a Panel at The CONSTRUMAT Event in Barcelona	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/30/the-ashvin-project-was-featured-in-a-panel-at-the-construmat-event-in-barcelona/
23/05/2023	ASHVIN’s 2nd Webinar on Digital Twin Tools Supporting Maintenance Raised the Interest of more than 130 Stakeholders	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/23/ashvins-2nd-webinar-on-digital-twin-tools-supporting-maintenance-raised-the-interest-of-more-than-130-stakeholders/
18/05/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #9 “Sports Stadium Roof Structure” – Support to Asset Maintenance with Digital Twins	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/18/ashvin-demo-site-9-sports-stadium-roof-structure-support-to-asset-maintenance-with-digital-twins/
02/05/2023	ASHVIN’s Approach to Safety in the Construction Industry	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/05/02/ashvins-approach-to-safety-in-the-construction-industry/
18/04/2023	UPC Hosts a Seminar about ASHVIN at the College of Engineering, University of Notre Dame, US	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/04/18/upc-hosts-a-seminar-about-ashvin-at-the-college-of-engineering-university-of-notre-dame-us/
17/04/2023	Join us on the 23rd of May at ASHVIN’s Technical Webinar #2!	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/04/17/join-us-on-the-23rd-of-may-at-ashvins-technical-webinar-2/
17/04/2023	ASHVIN Booklet on Innovation for Construction Site Managers is Here!	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/04/17/ashvin-booklet-on-innovation-for-construction-site-managers-is-here/
14/04/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #7 Research Presented in a Conference Paper at NASCC: Steel Conference, in Charlotte, US	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/04/14/ashvin-demo-site-7-research-presented-in-a-conference-paper-at-nascc-steel-conference-in-charlotte-us/
11/04/2023	ASHVIN Enables Visualisation of Construction Activities with its Digital Twin Platform	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/04/11/ashvin-enables-visualisation-of-construction-activities-with-its-digital-twin-platform/
31/03/2023	Innovation and Creativity: Problem-Solving through Digital Solutions in the Construction Sector	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/03/31/innovation-and-creativity-problem-solving-through-digital-solutions-in-the-construction-sector/
24/03/2023	ASHVIN Attended the SmartBuilt4EU Project Final Conference	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/03/24/ashvin-attended-the-smartbuilt4eu-project-final-conference/
16/03/2023	ASHVIN Demo Site #3 “Airport Runway in Croatia” Successfully Conducted	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/03/16/ashvin-demo-site-3-airport-runway-in-croatia-successfully-conducted/
28/02/2023	Open Call for Construction Projects to Deploy the ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/28/open-call-for-construction-projects-to-deploy-the-ashvin-digital-twin-platform/
28/02/2023	Successful Technical Webinar about the ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/28/successful-technical-webinar-about-the-ashvin-digital-twin-platform/
24/02/2023	ASHVIN’s Innovation Presented at Livestream of “Think Wireless IoT Days”	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/24/ashvins-innovation-presented-at-livestream-of-think-wireless-iot-days/

14/02/2023	ASHVIN is featured in the Smart Buildings Future Technologies brochure	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/14/ashvin-is-featured-in-the-smart-buildings-future-technologies-brochure/
13/02/2023	ASHVIN Digital Twin Platform: Join our Open Technical Webinar on the 28th of February!	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/13/ashvin-digital-twin-platform-join-our-open-technical-webinar-on-the-28th-of-february/
13/02/2023	ASHVIN Advisory Board Underlines the Importance of Standards in Data Management	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/13/ashvin-advisory-board-underlines-the-importance-of-standards-in-data-management/
10/02/2023	ASHVIN Observes the International Day of Women and Girls in Science	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/10/ashvin-observes-the-international-day-of-women-and-girls-in-science/
03/02/2023	Exploitation Workshop among 4 Digital Twin Innovation Projects	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/03/exploitation-workshop-among-4-digital-twin-innovation-projects/
02/02/2023	ASHVIN Collaborates with IMSAFE Project on Standardisation	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/02/ashvin-collaborates-with-imsafe-project-on-standardisation/
02/02/2023	ASHVIN Looks into Evidence-Based Design to Boost Productivity and Safety in Construction	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/02/02/ashvin-looks-into-evidence-based-design-to-boost-productivity-and-safety-in-construction/
24/01/2023	Monitoring data from sensors: A smart data approach	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/01/24/detecting-anomalies-and-de-noising-monitoring-data-from-sensors-a-smart-data-approach/
24/01/2023	Beyond the ASHVIN Tools: Training and Upskilling	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/01/24/beyond-the-ashvin-tools-training-and-upskilling/
24/01/2023	Detecting anomalies and de-noising monitoring data from sensors: A smart data approach	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/01/24/detecting-anomalies-and-de-noising-monitoring-data-from-sensors-a-smart-data-approach/
20/01/2023	5th Consortium Meeting in Greece	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/01/20/the-5th-consortium-meeting-in-greece/
03/01/2023	The Advisory Board Guides ASHVIN towards the Future Construction Industry	https://www.ashvin.eu/2023/01/03/the-advisory-board-guides-ashvin-towards-the-future-construction-industry/
22/12/2022	Real-time duration extraction of crane works for data-driven discrete event simulation	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/22/real-time-duration-extraction-of-crane-works-for-data-driven-discrete-event-simulation/
22/12/2022	A survey for image-based methods in construction: from images to digital twins	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/22/a-survey-for-image-based-methods-in-construction-from-images-to-digital-twins/
22/12/2022	On the digital twinning of routine load tests in railway bridges	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/22/on-the-digital-twinning-of-routine-load-tests-in-railway-bridges/
22/12/2022	Ground-Based interferometer radars for load tests of long-span arch bridges	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/22/ground-based-interferometer-radars-for-load-tests-of-long-span-arch-bridges/
22/12/2022	Platology: A Digital Twin Ontology Suite for the Complete Lifecycle of Infrastructure	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/22/platology-a-digital-twin-ontology-suite-for-the-complete-lifecycle-of-infrastructure/
20/12/2022	ASHVIN's YEAR-2 Review with the European Commission	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/12/20/ashvins-year-2-review-with-the-european-commission/
21/11/2022	Taking the Stock of ASHVIN as Entering the Final Project Year	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/21/taking-the-stock-of-ashvin-as-entering-the-final-project-year/
18/11/2022	Meeting of the Four LC-008-EB Sister Projects in November 2022	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/18/meeting-of-the-four-lc-008-eb-sister-projects-in-november-2022/
14/11/2022	ASHVIN Demo Site #5 "Kineum Office Building" in Sweden is Running	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/14/ashvin-demo-site-5-kineum-office-building-in-sweden-is-running/
11/11/2022	ASHVIN Will Deploy the BuildingSMART Use Cases	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/11/11/ashvin-will-deploy-the-buildingsmart-use-cases/
27/10/2022	ASHVIN at the Jornada de Digitalización de Infraestructuras Lineales, Madrid	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/27/ashvin-at-the-jornada-de-digitalizacion-de-infraestructuras-lineales-madrid/
24/10/2022	ASHVIN Represented in Panel Discussions about Digital Twins as Business Opportunity at the The District Show	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/24/ashvin-represented-in-panel-discussions-about-digital-twins-as-business-opportunity-at-the-the-district-show/
14/10/2022	ASHVIN is Working on Proposing a European Wide Digital Twin Standard	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/14/ashvin-is-working-on-proposing-a-european-wide-digital-twin-standard/

10/10/2022	ASHVIN Demo Site #1 Successfully Finalized	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/10/ashvin-demo-site-1-successfully-finalized/
06/10/2022	ASHVIN Presented at the 9th Greek Technology Forum in Thessaloniki	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/10/06/ashvin-presented-at-the-9th-greek-technology-forum-in-thessaloniki/
06/06/2022	POSITIONING ASHVIN TO THE MARKET	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/06/06/positioning-ashvin-to-the-market/
22/05/2022	DIGITAL TWIN: CONCEPT, OBJECTIVES AND METHODS	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/05/22/digital-twin-concept-objectives-and-methods/
05/05/2022	ASHVIN's Value Proposition!	https://www.ashvin.eu/2022/05/05/ashvins-value-proposition/